

EELISA

European University

COST-BENEFIT ANALYSIS OF EELISA INNOCORE ACTIONS

Deliverable 1.5

Date: 31 May, 2024

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

Technical references

Grant Agreement number:	101035811
Project Acronym:	EELISA innoCORE
Project title:	EELISA INNOVation and Common Research strategy
Start date of the project:	1 June 2021
Duration of the project:	36 months

Deliverable No.:	1.5 Cost-Benefit Analysis of EELISA InnoCORE actions
Work Package:	1
Task:	1.5 Cost-Benefit Analysis
Lead beneficiary:	UPM
Due date of deliverable:	31 May 2024
Actual submission date:	31 May 2024
Dissemination level:	Public

Document history

V	Date	WP Leader	Reviewed by:
1	25/04/2024	UPM	First version sent to EELISA partners for review. The deliverable has been produced out of an extensive consultation process that started in December 2023. Reviewed by all partners.
2	30/04/2024	UPM	Reviewed version presented to EELISA partners during WP1 meeting. Reviewed by all partners.
3	08/05/2024	UPM	Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies, performing 1 st quality check.
4	23/05/2024	UPM	Presentation of deliverable and results to EELISA Executive Board.
5	24/05/2024	UPM	Final version

Acknowledgement: This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811.

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EELISA InnoCORE Partners

Number	Role	Name in original language	Name in English	Short name	Country
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2	BEN	École Nationale des Ponts et Chaussées	National School of Civil Engineering	ENPC	France
3	BEN	Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg	Friedrich-Alexander University Erlangen-Nürnberg	FAU	Germany
4	BEN	İstanbul Teknik Üniversitesi	Istanbul Technical University	ITU	Turkey
5	BEN	Scuola Normale Superiore	Higher Normal School	SNS	Italy
6	BEN	Scuola Superiore di Studi Universitari e di Perfezionamento Sant'Anna	Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies	SSSA	Italy
7	BEN	Universitatea Politehnica din Bucuresti	Politehnica University of Bucharest	UPB	Romania
8	BEN	Budapesti Műszaki és Gazdaságtudományi Egyetem	Budapest University of Technology and Economics	BME	Hungary
9	BEN	Université Paris Sciences et Lettres	Université PSL	PSL	France

Alliance members

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Executive summary

This deliverable has been produced as part of the **evaluation of EELISA InnoCORE** (EELISA INNOVation and Common Research strategy) and is prepared within the work package WP1 – ‘Coordination, evaluation, communication and dissemination’.

D1.5 explores, in broad qualitative and quantitative terms, the costs and benefits of 20 key actions implemented under EELISA InnoCORE. The actions are classified according to the seven institutional transformation modules (ITMs) InnoCORE has been working on, therefore, giving an insight on the impact achieved under each of them. The cost- benefit comparison involved four steps: 1) selecting the actions to be assessed, 2) identifying and describing costs and benefits, 3) scoring (quantifying) costs and benefits, 4) assessment. See section 1.

For the quantification of benefits and costs, given the difficulty of quantifying benefits in monetary terms, EELISA InnoCORE produced a scoring system using a 1 to 4 scale as explained in section 1) Methodology. The identification of costs and benefits considers four different target groups: researchers and innovators, administrative staff, the individual EELISA partner institutions, the broader community, and the European Union and the European Research Area.

After the description of the methodology (section 1) and the list of actions selected (section 2), section 3 includes a thorough assessment of the costs and benefits identified, including the assessment of the benefits and costs for the project as a whole (section 3.1) and an assessment per ITM (section 3.2). The annexes include: the templates used for identifying costs and benefits (qualitative assessment) and all the input gathered; the template used for scoring costs and benefits (quantitative assessment) and a table used for producing the dispersion graphs compiling the scores per partner.

Assessing the impact and costs of actions is essential for the future of EELISA. European University Alliances are meant to be long-lasting initiatives with a much broader ambition than a mere three-year project. Having a thorough evaluation of actions will ease taking the right decisions for the long-term vision of our Alliance. **The analysis performed herein tries to answer some fundamental questions for the continuation of the R&I dimension of EELISA: which actions had a very good impact and might be worth continuing, which actions were very successful but took important resources, which actions had a more limited impact and should be reviewed.**

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Review by EELISA

In order to guarantee coordination and complementarity and avoid overlapping between the two projects, the EELISA office has been consulted for the production of this deliverable.

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Glossary- Abbreviations and definitions

(alphabetic order)

Definitions for gender specific terms included below have been taken from EIGE's Glossary¹.

CA. Consortium Agreement. The consortium agreement is a private agreement between the beneficiaries, to set out the rights and obligations amongst themselves. (It does NOT involve the European Commission/Agency.)

C&B. Cost Benefits.

EELISA Community. The EELISA communities are mission-driven working groups that bring together students, teachers, and researchers from all partner universities with prestigious professionals, grassroots organizations, citizens, private companies, and public institutions to find innovative solutions to real-world challenges.

EELISA Cluster. EELISA Clusters are science-based working groups that will work on the scientific and technological solutions that may contribute to solve the societal challenges identified by EELISA Communities.

EINP. EELISA InnoCORE Networking Platform.

ERA. European Research Area. The European Research Area is the ambition to create a single, borderless market for research, innovation and technology across the EUT. The ERA is based on excellence and: prioritizes investments and reforms in research and innovation; boosts market uptake; strengthens mobility of researchers and free flow of knowledge and technology; improves access to excellence.

ERA Actions. The ERA policy framework includes the ERA Policy Agenda which in turn sets out 20 voluntary ERA actions for the period 2022-2024 to contribute to the priority areas defined in the Council Recommendation on a Pact for Research and Innovation in Europe (Pact for R&I).

GA. Grant Agreement. This is the grant contract concluded between the EU and the beneficiaries. It establishes the rights and obligations that govern the grant. It consists of a core text and annexes (for instance, fixing the project content and the project budget).

GEP. Gender Equality Plan. In the specific context of research organisations and higher education institutions, the European Commission considers a Gender Equality Plan as a set of actions aimed at: 1. conducting impact assessment/audits of procedures and practices to identify gender bias; 2. identifying and implementing innovative strategies to correct any bias; 3. setting targets and monitoring progress via indicators (1).

HEIs. Higher Education Institutions.

ITM. Institutional Transformation Module. The key objective of the call Horizon 2020 IBA-SwafS-Support-1-2020 that funded EELISA InnoCORE was to utilise the 'European Universities' as a testbed for exploring support for institutional transformation in their research and innovation dimension. For this, the call proposed seven transformation modules. EELISA InnoCORE proposed actions under all the seven ITMs.

¹ <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/concepts-and-definitions>

PLB. Policy Liaisons Board. The PLB is a group of experts in EU projects and EU policy-making from each EELISA partner institution. Its tasks include identifying opportunities for discussion at EU level; liaising with peers and representing EELISA in relevant activities; or identifying and sharing opportunities to continue or to further increase the collaboration of EELISA partners in research and innovation.

SDGs. Sustainable Development Goals. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), also known as the Global Goals, were adopted by the United Nations in 2015 as a universal call to action to end poverty, protect the planet, and ensure that by 2030 all people enjoy peace and prosperity. There are 17 SDGs.

TTO. Technology Transfer Office. TTOs are units within universities responsible for commercialising university owned intellectual property through the core activities of: attracting and assessing invention disclosures; patenting and other forms of intellectual property protection; licensing; spin-out company formation; material sales; managing seed funds. The TTO may also incorporate a function that helps researchers sell their time as expert consultants. The TTO is separate to the Research Office, which will typically support university researchers in identifying and winning research funding, and manage the contractual relationships with research funders.

Table of content

Technical references.....	2
Document history	2
EELISA InnoCORE Partners.....	3
Executive summary	4
List of contacts contributing to D1.5 Cost & Benefit Analyses	5
Review by EELISA.....	5
Glossary- Abbreviations and definitions	6
1 Methodology	10
2 The 20 key actions assessed.....	14
3 Cost-benefit analysis	16
3.1 Overview – EELISA InnoCORE	16
3.1.1 The benefits of EELISA InnoCORE actions	16
3.1.2 The costs of EELISA InnoCORE actions	18
3.1.3 Scoring the benefits and costs of EELISA InnoCORE actions	19
3.2 Assessment per Institutional Transformation Module.....	23
3.2.1 ITM1 Developing a common R&I agenda and action plan	23
3.2.2 ITM2 Strengthening human capital, enabling balanced brain circulation and gender balance	25
3.2.3 ITM3 Sharing infrastructures and other resources	27
3.2.4 ITM4 Reinforcing cooperation with non-academic actors, especially academia-business cooperation, with targeted actions aimed to put our innovations in the market	28
3.2.5 ITM5 Mainstreaming of comprehensive Open Science practices	30
3.2.6 ITM6 Involvement of citizens, civil society and public/cities authorities in research and innovation.....	32
3.2.7 ITM7 – Exploring joint structures across the European Universities.....	33
4 Recommendations for the improvement of EELISA InnoCORE actions	34
Annex I – Template used for the identification and description of costs and benefits ..	39
Annex II – Identifying costs and benefits: whole input gathered from partners	40
ITM1 Developing a common research and innovation agenda and action plan....	40
ITM2 Strengthening human capital, enabling balanced brain circulation and gender balance	45
ITM3 Sharing research infrastructures and other resources.....	53
ITM4 Reinforcing cooperation with non-academic actors, especially academia-business cooperation; with targeted actions aimed to put our innovations in the market	56
ITM5 Mainstreaming of comprehensive Open Science practices	67

ITM6 Involvement of citizens, civil society and public/cities authorities in research and innovation	75
ITM7 Exploring joint structures across the European Universities on technical activities common to all “European Universities”	80
Annex III - Scores per partner	82

Table of figures

Figure 1: Steps of the methodology used for assessing the costs and benefits of EELISA InnoCORE actions.....	10
Figure 2: Costs and benefits graph of EELISA InnoCORE actions – Averages.....	19
Figure 3: Costs and benefits graph of EELISA InnoCORE action – Normalized score range.	20
Figure 4: Costs and benefits graph of EELISA InnoCORE actions – Clustering benefits	21
Figure 5: Costs and benefits graph of EELISA InnoCORE actions – Clustering costs.....	22
Figure 6: Costs and benefits graph of actions under ITM1 - Developing a common research and innovation agenda and action plan	24
Figure 7: Costs and benefits graph of actions under ITM2 - Strengthening human capital, enabling balanced brain circulation and gender balance.....	26
Figure 8: Costs and benefits graph of actions under ITM3 Sharing infrastructures and other resources.....	27
Figure 9: Costs and benefits graph of actions under ITM4 Reinforcing cooperation with no-academic actors, especially academia-business cooperation, with targeted actions aimed to put our innovations in the market.....	29
Figure 10: Costs and benefits graph of actions under ITM5 Mainstreaming of comprehensive Open Science practices	31
Figure 11: Costs and benefits graph of actions under ITM6 Involvement of citizens, civil society and public/cities authorities in research and innovation.....	32
Figure 12: Costs and benefits graph of actions under ITM7 – Exploring joint structures across the European Universities.....	33
Figure 13: Costs and benefits graph of actions – Describing actions and measures to be taken.....	34

1 Methodology

The cost- benefit comparison performed to produce D1.5 involved four steps as illustrated in Figure 1: 1) selecting the actions to be assessed, 2) identifying and describing costs and benefits in qualitative terms, 3) scoring (quantifying) the costs and benefits identified in the second step, 4) C&B balance and assessment.

For the identification of costs and benefits (step 2), partners were asked to fill in the template included as Annex I – Template used for the identification and description of costs and benefits, for each of the 20 key actions assessed. The **identification of C&B considers both short-term and long-term benefits and costs, and five different target groups: researchers and innovators, administrative staff, our institutions, the society and broader community, and lastly the European Union and the European Research Area.** This brainstorming exercise run between December 2023 and January 2024 and all the input gathered can be found in Annex II – Identifying costs and benefits: whole input gathered from partners.

Figure 1: Steps of the methodology used for assessing the costs and benefits of EELISA InnoCORE actions

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After defining costs and benefits, EELISA InnoCORE partners were asked to score the 20 selected actions by **rating benefits and costs against three parameters using for each parameter a scale of 1 to 4**, as explained below. Partners were asked to use whole numbers with no decimals.

When deciding about the methodology to be used, it seemed clear that the quantification of costs in monetary terms could be feasible. However, valuing benefits seemed not feasible: given the public nature of EELISA and its partners, the actions put in place are not marketable. Moreover, the benefits obtained correspond in many cases to intangible assets. Because of this reason, EELISA InnoCORE decided to quantify C&B by using an ad hoc scale.

This scale is unique. It has been produced ad hoc by EELISA InnoCORE team for the evaluation of its actions, adapting it to the specificities and aims of the project, the Grant Agreement and to the ambition of DG RTD when launching the call that funded InnoCORE, i.e. to utilise the ‘European Universities’ as a testbed for exploring support for institutional transformation in their research and innovation dimension.

The **scores provided by partners have been turned into dispersion graphs to help visualize the cost-benefit of each of EELISA action** and to illustrate this deliverable. Scores per action and partner can be found in Annex III - Scores per partner.

SCALE USED FOR SCORING BENEFITS

<p style="text-align: center; color: #0070c0;">Transformation potential of the action for the institution & the Alliance as a whole (impact)</p> <p>4 = The action managed to generate very positive transformations and changes within the institution and the Alliance as a whole, it greatly helped in building the Alliance, and has the potential to continue to do so in the future. There is evidence enough that proves so.</p> <p>3 = The action managed to initiate some good transformations, helped in building the Alliance, and has potential to continue to do so for both the institution individually and for the Alliance as a whole in the future. There is a fair amount of evidence that proves so.</p> <p>2 = The action generated some but limited transformations within the institution and the Alliance as a whole. Its potential in building the Alliance was limited. There is a limited number of evidence.</p> <p>1 = The action had no impact within the institution nor the Alliance as a whole, triggered no changes and it is highly improbable that it can generate any positive changes in the future. There is hardly any evidence of the impact of the action.</p>
<p style="text-align: center; color: #0070c0;">Size of the target group, stakeholders or interested groups benefiting from the action</p> <p>4 = The action reached its target group and has gathered interest and involvement from a good-sized group of relevant stakeholders.</p> <p>3 = The action reached its target group and gathered a fair level of involvement from a fair-sized group of relevant stakeholders.</p>

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<p>2 = The action reached a small target group and gathered limited interest.</p> <p>1 = The action hardly reached its target group. Hardly anybody engaged or showed interest.</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Improvement of the excellence for the institution and the Alliance</p> <p>4 = The action managed to raise excellence within the institution and/or for the Alliance as a whole, both from an academic point of view as well as regarding management and procedural methods (e.g. project management).</p> <p>3 = The action managed to fairly improve or kickstart a process of raising excellence within the institution and/or for the Alliance as a whole, both from an academic point of view as well as regarding management and procedural methods (e.g. project management).</p> <p>2 = The action had limited impact in raising the excellence of the institution and/or for the Alliance as a whole, both from an academic point of view as well as regarding management and procedural methods (e.g. project management).</p> <p>1 = The action had no effect in the excellence of the institution and/or for the Alliance as a whole, both from an academic point of view as well as regarding management and procedural methods (e.g. project management).</p>

SCALE USED FOR SCORING COSTS

<p style="text-align: center;">Level of leadership needed</p> <p>1 = The action run / will run smoothly and did not require / will not require a heavy leadership.</p> <p>2 = The action run / will run fairly smoothly but required / will require some leadership directions to be implemented.</p> <p>3 = The action run / will run with some difficulties and required / will require the involvement of the top-management to be implemented.</p> <p>4 = The action run / will run with important difficulties and required / will require a very heavy leadership and involvement of the top management to be implemented.</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Workload for the people involved</p> <p>1 = The workload generated by the action was commensurate to its goals.</p> <p>2 = The workload generated by the action was important but not disproportionate.</p> <p>3 = The action generated a heavy workload, sometimes difficult to manage, and required dedicating some extra resources.</p> <p>4 = The action generated an overload, not commensurate to its goals, difficult to manage, and required dedicating extra resources.</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Associated risks</p> <p>1 = The risks associated to the action were low, did not materialize and, if so, they were manageable. The risks associated to the action are low, will probably not materialize and if so they will be manageable.</p>

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2 = The risks associated to the action were fair and, when they materialized, were manageable. The risks associated to the action are fair, might materialize but if so the Alliance will be able to manage them.

3 = The risks associated with the action were important, materialized and somehow diminished the benefits of the action. The risks associated with the action are important and could somehow diminish the benefits.

4 = The risks associated with the action were very high, materialized and importantly diminished the benefits of the action. The risks associated are very high and will probably materialize, diminishing the benefits of the action.

The following sections include an assessment of C&B based on the input gathered from the aforementioned exercises: qualitative description and identification of benefits and costs via step 2 and quantitative assessment via step 3.

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2 The 20 key actions assessed

EELISA InnoCORE partners selected the following 20 actions to be assessed. The selection of the actions considered several factors.

It is important to note that some actions correspond to single deliverables whose production and relevance were important enough to be considered a stand-out action. This is the case, for instance, of action 1, which corresponds to deliverable 2.1, or action 2, which corresponds to deliverable 2.5.

Some other actions gather several smaller actions or several documents or deliverables. This is the case, for instance, of actions 8, 9, 10 or 15. For example, action 15 includes several documents that are intrinsically interrelated: indeed, partners have used the OS methodological toolkit and guidelines to update their individual OS actions plans. Therefore, it was decided to assess the production and use of these documents as a single action. This is the case also for action 9, which considers several strategic documents that are interlinked regarding infrastructures.

Other actions correspond to platforms, e.g. the EELISA InnoCORE networking platform (action 4) or the Open Science Training Hub (action 17), or to actions that can be easily singled out because they had a very specific aim or target group. For instance, the Next Level Competition and the Entrepreneurship School are separated in different actions because, although being under the same ITM, i.e. bringing innovation into the market, their target public is very different.

The 20 key actions assessed

ITM1 Developing a common research and innovation agenda and action plan	1	Mapping of strategic research areas of all the members (D2.1)
	2	Portfolio of the potential of challenges revealed in first EELISA Communities with identification of scientific and technological needs (D2.5)
	3	Organization of symposia with representatives of R&I structures (D2.2 and D2.4)
ITM2 Strengthening human capital, enabling balanced brain circulation and gender balance	4	EELISA InnoCORE Networking Platform (EINP) (WP5)
	5	EELISA Connect open call for workshops (WP5)
	6	EELISA Gender and Diversity Work Group (WP1)
	7	EELISA InnoCORE Policy Liaisons Board (WP1)
ITM3 Sharing infrastructures and other resources	8	EELISA Catalogue of facilities (portfolio of infrastructures and equipment and IT implementation of the catalogue) (D4.1 and D4.3)
	9	Coordinate infrastructure strategy (D4.4) and definition of a roadmap on research infrastructures (D2.4) and definition of the framework conditions for joint infrastructures (D4.5)

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ITM4 Reinforcing cooperation with non-academic actors especially academia-business cooperation, with targeted actions aimed to put our innovations in the market	10	Production and use of the following documents: Plan for collaborative RDI, technology transfer and innovation ecosystems (D6.2), Science Park model (D6.1) and recommendations for novel structures for governance: academic and industrial participation (D6.3)
	11	1st EELISA Industrial Chair (MS6, WP6)
	12	EELISA Co-creation, Entrepreneurship and Innovation processes: sharing of and opening activities (WP7)
	13	EELISA Entrepreneurship School (WP7)
	14	EELISA Start-up competition (WP7)
ITM5 Mainstreaming comprehensive Open Science practices	15	Production and use of OS Methodological Toolkit (D3.1) and OS Strategic Planning and Implementation Guide (D3.2) and Updated OS Institutional policies and actions plans (D3.3)
	16	Network of Open Science Ambassadors (D3.6, task 3.5)
	17	Innovative Distributed OS training Hub (D3.4, task 3.3)
ITM6 Involvement of citizens, civil society and public/cities authorities in research and innovation	18	EELISA Innovation Talks (WP7)
	19	EELISA Prototype Contest (WP7)
IMT7 – Exploring joint structures across European universities	20	Participation in FOREU meetings and activities, including events organised by other alliances (CHARM-EU, Exper, CIVIS)

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3 Cost-benefit analysis

3.1 Overview – EELISA InnoCORE

As explained in Section 1, EELISA InnoCORE partners identified costs and benefits, both in the short and the long-term in qualitative terms for what we consider to be the main five target groups or beneficiaries of EELISA InnoCORE: a) our researchers and innovators; b) our administrative staff, c) our individual institutions, d) society as a whole, as well as e) the European Union and the European Research Area. Below we summarize the main findings.

3.1.1 The benefits of EELISA InnoCORE actions

Researchers and innovators

Regarding EELISA researchers and innovators, the keyword regarding the benefits brought by InnoCORE is an increased number of **opportunities** in many senses. The actions put in place under InnoCORE provided our researchers and innovators with an increased number of **networking opportunities both with peers** (networking platform, EELISA Connect, R&I symposia, Entrepreneurship School) as well as **with key external stakeholders** (e.g. the aim of the Next Level competition was to put our innovators in contact with investors); **training and competence development opportunities** in different aspects (gender dimension in research, open science training hub, innovation and entrepreneurship training initiatives); opportunities to **get access to extra funding to organize activities**, particularly, via the EELISA Connect call for workshops; or opportunities to have **access to facilities not available at the host institution** (e.g. JOSPEHS innovation lab). The main outcome of this has been, in turn, the **initiation of new R&I collaborations**, e.g. EELISA researchers are working in various project proposals as an outcome of EELISA Connect workshops.

Administrative staff

It is important to note that EELISA **InnoCORE actions have also brought very important benefits for EELISA administrative staff and research managers**. Strengthening the strategic capacity of Europe's public research performing and funding organizations will only be possible if our institutions can rely on strong and well-equipped research management structures, able to support complex collaborative projects. In this regard, thanks to EELISA InnoCORE, our administrative staff have been exposed to diverse administrative practices and policies, being able to **learn from more experienced partners with more consolidated schemes**. As a concrete example, in the case of academia-business collaboration, EELISA partners have not only shared good practices, but also there has been a **direct exchange of hands-on documentation** (framework agreements of ownership transfer of intellectual property rights; co-ownership agreement; distribution of royalties among inventors). Likewise, for our European and International project offices.

EELISA administrative staff have been able to find sources of inspiration for refining or putting in place new services and policies within their institutions. They also had, as in the case of researchers and innovators, an increased number of opportunities: networking opportunities with both peers and external stakeholders, and skills development opportunities (e.g. peer learning performed by the gender equality units or by our European Project offices and our TTOs). If we were to choose the keywords regarding benefits for this group have been **mutual learning and, as an outcome, the creation of communities of practice**. Lastly, EELISA partners highlight that, as a result and as a clear benefit, InnoCORE has meant an **enhanced professional growth and development for the administrative staff**.

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The institution

Together with the aforementioned benefits for researchers and innovators and administrative staff, which can be considered benefits for the institution as a whole — indeed having better skilled staff or being able to offer more opportunities to researchers are clear benefits for our institutions—, EELISA InnoCORE actions have given EELISA partners **greater visibility** at EU level and have contributed to **reinforce the connections** of our institutions with policy-makers at EU, national and regional level (e.g. via the Policy Liaison Board or FOREU activities), with other Alliances and peer universities (via FOREU) **as well as with external stakeholders, including industry** (e.g. via the R&I symposia, the Next Level Competition or the Entrepreneurship School).

EELISA InnoCORE actions also provided our institutions with **international benchmarks for various dimensions**, particularly research performance (thanks to the mapping of EELISA strategic research areas) or gender equality (thanks to the collection of sex-disaggregated data). As already mentioned, EELISA InnoCORE gave EELISA institutions the possibility to **enrich their individual offers** (training offer, access to infrastructures and facilities, funding offer). In the medium term, having joint portfolios of services and resources will mean a better exploitation of individual resources by finding synergies and avoiding duplication.

Society and broader community

EELISA partners have also identified the benefits that InnoCORE brought to society. In this regard, it is worth noting that many InnoCORE actions (mapping strategic research areas, EELISA Connect workshops, networking platform) have SDGs in focus. Therefore, **the contribution of EELISA to SDGs could be traced in the future** by iterating the same methodology.

EELISA InnoCORE actions also meant a better exploitation of resources by finding synergies and enriching our individual university offers. The budget of universities being mainly public, this clearly means a **better use of public moneys and a benefit for society**.

EELISA InnoCORE actions also contributed to the promotion of **broadly accepted common good principles, such as: gender equality and diversity, the vindication of the role of women in science; the promotion of open science and FAIR principles**, having as a result enhanced public access to research outputs, contributing to knowledge dissemination and education; or the **promotion of entrepreneurship mindset** among researchers and students, and the valorization of research results by bringing ideas into the market.

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Lastly, EELISA InnoCORE actions played their part in **advancing ERA**, contributing to a whole array of ERA actions:

- Action 1: Enable the open sharing of knowledge and the re-use of research outputs, including through the development of the European open science cloud (EOSC).
- Action 2: Advance towards the reform the assessment system for research, researchers and institutions to improve their quality, performance and impact.
- Action 5 Promote gender equality and foster inclusiveness, taking note of the Ljubljana declaration.
- Action 7 Better knowledge valorisation.
- Action 8 Strengthen sustainability, accessibility and resilience of research infrastructures in the ERA.
- Action 13 Empower higher education institutions to develop in line with the era, and in synergy with the European education area.
- Action 14: Bring science closer to citizens.
- Action 17 Enhance the strategic capacity of Europe’s public research performing organisations.

EELISA partners consider that InnoCORE also contributed to **build Europe** in different ways: from contributing to the **harmonization and Europeanisation of regulations and practices** (protocol for industrial chairs, open science action plans); to showcasing EU-funded research and innovation projects, and thus enhancing the visibility of EU support for researchers and innovators; and reinforcing **the sense of belonging to the EU. By creating international collaboration teams** and working on boosting the sense of belonging to EELISA, InnoCORE has also contributed at the same time to reinforce the sense of ownership and belonging to the European Union.

3.1.2 The costs of EELISA InnoCORE actions

Implementing EELISA InnoCORE actions had obvious costs in terms of human resources and time spent by our researchers, innovators and administrative staff in designing, coordinating, implementing or contributing to the various actions; travel, accommodation and subsistence for participating in onsite activities; dissemination and communication material; costs related to the development of the IT tools (networking platform, catalogue of infrastructures, OS training hub). These being obvious costs, we would like to highlight here other type of more specific costs pointed out by EELISA partners when identifying costs and benefits. **Some should be considered ‘risks’ rather than ‘actual costs’** but that we think are important to highlight.

Firstly, for some actions, EELISA partners point out to the **extra workload** that InnoCORE generated **for the permanent staff**. EELISA partners hired project managers and allocated internal staff for implementing EELISA InnoCORE, however, as already highlighted in the policy brief (1), at certain points this came at the expense of stretching human resources at its maximum. Another particular cost of InnoCORE actions has been the **translation into English** of material. Sharing resources needed the translation of material from the language of the hosting institution into English as lingua franca.

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Another costs, or rather risk, that partners point out for almost all actions is their continuation and the linked **potential discontinuation**. Keeping InnoCORE tools alive and updated (update of the research strategy and the mapping of research areas, continuation of the networking platform, tweaking of the catalogue of infrastructures, monitoring of the industrial chair and update of the protocol, and many more) will require dedicating resources. Whereas this risk has been minimized via EELISA 2.0 —many tools and initiatives will be taken over by EELISA 2.0 guaranteeing its full exploitation—, EELISA InnoCORE partners fear that EELISA 2.0 will not be able to cover the costs of some initiatives. For instance, whereas EELISA Connect is considered the action that generated the highest level of benefits for EELISA partners and the Alliance (see next section), the target group and scope of the future EELISA joint call diverts from EELISA Connect. In this sense, the discontinuation of some initiatives will entail certain **costs in terms of false expectations and inability of fully exploiting the momentum created by InnoCORE**.

3.1.3 Scoring the benefits and costs of EELISA InnoCORE actions

After defining costs and benefits, EELISA InnoCORE partners were asked to score the 20 selected actions by rating benefits and costs against three parameters using for each parameter a scale 1 to 4, as explained in section 1.

The scores provided by partners have been turned into dispersion graphs to help visualize the cost-benefit of each of EELISA action. Figure 2 uses plain averages. In Figure 3, the answers have been normalized to the maximum and minimum scores, so that the scoring ranges are the same for all partners. For the sake of accurateness, we will use the graph in Figure 3 for the current assessment.

Figure 2: Costs and benefits graph of EELISA InnoCORE actions – Averages.

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Figure 3: Costs and benefits graph of EELISA InnoCORE action – Normalized score range.

As Figure 4 shows **over half of the actions assessed (12 actions) generated high or very high benefits for EELISA institutions individually as well of EELISA as a whole.**

The action that got the **highest scores regarding benefits is the EELISA Connect call for workshops** (action 5), followed by the **Next Level competition** (action 14) and the **opening up of innovation, cocreation and entrepreneurial activities** (action 12). Indeed, **for the three actions and for the three parameters considered, EELISA partners give these actions a score over 3.5 on average**, meaning that the actions managed to generate or initiate very positive transformations, greatly helped in building the Alliance and have the potential to continue to do so in the future. The actions reached its target group and gathered the involvement of a good-sized grouped of stakeholders. The three actions initiated a process of raising excellence “both from an academic point of view as well as regarding management and procedural methods (e.g. project management)”. In this regard, it is important to note this last aspect: as highlighted above, **many InnoCORE actions helped our institutions improve their procedural methods**, partners found inspiration for improving their own services and their administrative staff gained new skills.

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Figure 4: Costs and benefits graph of EELISA InnoCORE actions – Clustering benefits

Close to these three actions, **nine other actions follow** in terms of benefits: the prototype contest (9), the mapping of the EELISA Strategic Research Areas (action 1) and the R&I symposia (3), followed by the open science guidelines and action plans (OS toolkit, action 15), the networking platform (action 4), the gender equality and diversity work group (action 6), the participation in FOREU (action 20), the Policy Liaisons Board (action 7) and the Entrepreneurship School (action 13), most of them with **scores between 3 (or very close to 3) and 3.5**. I.e. these actions managed to initiate good transformations and kickstarted a process of raising excellence, both within the individual institutions as well as for EELISA as a whole.

Following this, we have a group of six actions having had a fair-medium impact on EELISA InnoCORE partners individually and the Alliance (with scores on average under three but in general over 2.5), and two actions having generated somehow limited benefits. There might be some factors that explain the lower impact of these actions, very particularly **not having reached enough maturity** (the OS training hub was launched only recently, the catalogue of facilities is not yet fully operational).

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Figure 5: Costs and benefits graph of EELISA InnoCORE actions – Clustering costs

Regarding costs, it is to be noted that EELISA InnoCORE partners consider that **most of the actions had a very fair level of costs**: in general terms, the actions run fairly smoothly, the workload generated was important but not disproportionate and the risks were manageable.

Five actions lie in the high-cost quadrant. The action that EELISA partners consider that had the highest level of costs is the catalogue of facilities (action 8). The action is running with some difficulties, requiring the involvement of the top management of our institutions, it needed the allocation of extra resources and the risks associated with it materialized. Indeed, **the IT implementation of the catalogue is proving to be a challenge requiring an important level of resources**. In connection with this, the development of the strategies, roadmaps and documents related to infrastructures and facilities (action 9) are also posing challenges and generating important costs, probably due to the complexity of the topic. The setting up and launching of the networking platform (action 4) also generated an important workload and needed the allocation of extra resources: again, **the implementation of actions that require IT solutions are in general terms requiring important resources** (in its first policy brief, EELISA InnoCORE partners already pointed out to the digitalization and digitation of resources as an important challenge that the Alliance was facing). Lastly, although the mapping of the strategic research areas was a key exercise for the Alliance, it required important resources due to the lack of automatized data retrieval systems and to the fact that the collection relied on manual collection.

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3.2 Assessment per Institutional Transformation Module

3.2.1 ITM1 Developing a common R&I agenda and action plan

ITM1 Developing a common research and innovation agenda and action plan

Regarding the concrete benefits of **Action 1**), the **mapping of strategic research areas (SRAs)** provided EELISA partners with **insightful information regarding capacities** and with a **better knowledge of “both already and potential collaborations”**, which was a needed exercise to set the foundations of the R&I dimension of EELISA. Since the mapping was run at the beginning of the InnoCORE project, this exercise can be used as a **benchmark for the future assessment of the impact of EELISA on the R&I results** of its partners. Together with this, partners also highlight as main benefits the link of the SRAs with the SDGs (*long term benefits*): thanks to this connection, the **contribution of EELISA to SDGs could be traced in the future** by iterating the same methodology. Regarding costs, due to the lack of automatized systems, the data collection required an important amount of time, efforts and resources. Most importantly, running a regular and systematic **update and maintenance of the database needs extensive resources** (including subscription fees to databases such as Scival), which represents an important long-term cost.

EELISA InnoCORE analyzed the **challenges revealed in the first EELISA Communities via deliverable 2.5, Action 2)**. This report provided EELISA partners with important input regarding the needs of researchers, **allowing the Alliance to design more adapted tools and resources for researchers**. Indeed, D2.5 has been used under EELISA 2.0 for the design of the joint calls. For the administrative staff, the input gathered has also been a way of gaining experience on research management thanks to the feedback from researchers. These being the main benefits, the main cost is and will remain in the long term the **lack of automatized data collections systems** that make the collection mainly a manual work requiring an important amount of resources.

Action 3) ‘Organization of the two symposia with representatives of R&I structures’ generated important benefits for EELISA and its partner institutions. The symposia provided EELISA partners with **increased networking opportunities, very particularly for and among their research and innovation support units** —technology transfer offices, European and international project management departments, industrial chair experts, entrepreneurship support units and others. The **reinforcement of the collaboration** achieved paved the way for the setting up and launching initiatives that, **in turn, generated new opportunities for researchers and innovators** (entrepreneurship action plan, protocol of industrial chairs, network of European project offices, etc.). This will sure bring a better exploitation of individual resources by finding synergies and avoiding duplication, which represents a clear long-term benefit for all stakeholders, not only EELISA partners but also society (via a better use of public resources).

Scoring benefits and costs

In connection with the general parameters used for the scoring (see Figure 6), the mapping of EELISA SRAs as well as the organization of the symposia have been key actions for EELISA InnoCORE: both actions managed to generate very good transformations, greatly helped in building the Alliance, and reached its target group. At the same time, and particularly for action 1), the mapping of SRAs took important efforts —second one with the highest scores regarding costs: indeed, the collection of data generated a heavy workload, difficult to manage at certain times, that required extra resources and an important involvement of the top management to be implemented. Lastly, the production of deliverable 2.5 had a more limited impact on EELISA institutions. This is probably due to the fact that the report has been mainly a theoretical exercise that, although currently being used under EELISA 2.0, has been less used under EELISA InnoCORE.

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Figure 6: Costs and benefits graph of actions under ITM1 - Developing a common research and innovation agenda and action plan

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3.2.2 ITM2 Strengthening human capital, enabling balanced brain circulation and gender balance

ITM2 Strengthening human capital, enabling balanced brain circulation and gender balance

The launch of the **EELISA InnoCORE Networking Platform (EINP)** (action 4) and the **EELISA Connect open call for workshops** (action 5) brought its planned benefits to the Alliance, this is: an **increased number of networking opportunities for EELISA researchers** and an **increased visibility of their research activities**, and as an outcome, the **initiation of new research collaborations**. Another important benefit, the EELISA Connect call offered new opportunities for researchers to organize activities and to travel and visit infrastructures and facilities from other EELISA partners. This face-to-face contact has helped build the sense of belonging to EELISA European University. Both actions facilitated the identification of expertise within the Alliance, which is considered a clear benefit. Regarding costs, the initial building of the database for the EINP represented an important cost for the Alliance. EELISA partners also point out to the potential dropping of the tool and to the discontinuation of the calls due to the end of InnoCORE as potential risks that will entail costs in terms of missed opportunities and creation of false expectations.

The **EELISA Gender and Diversity Work Group** (action 6) generated the expected impact and benefits for the Alliance in terms of giving our researchers, our **administrative staff** (Gender Equality Units) and institutions opportunities for gaining new skills and knowledge, increased visibility and networking opportunities, and a better understanding of gender equality state-of-play at our institutions compared to peers (international benchmarking). The activities performed under the group led to the **creation of a community of practice**. EELISA partners point out to various benefits that this action brought for society as whole, such as the empowerment of women and the **vindication of the role of women in science**.

As in the case of action 6, the **EELISA InnoCORE Policy Liaisons Board** (action 7) has meant the creation of a community of practice, bringing an array of benefits for EELISA partners, particularly for the administrative staff (and more concretely for their **research managers**): **improvement of the skills, the capabilities and the services provided thanks to the mutual learning exercises and the exposure to diverse practices**. EELISA partners also point out to the greater visibility and having a **stronger voice in EU affairs** as key benefits of this action for the EELISA institutions.

The participation and contribution to the activities of these two groups —e.g. collection of sex-disaggregated data or production of position papers— have represented the main obvious costs of these two actions (6 and 7).

Scoring benefits and costs

The EELISA Connect call for workshops has been the action that, according to EELISA partners, brought the highest level of benefit to the Alliance and its partners institutions: EELISA Connect “managed to generate very positive transformations and changes within the institution and the Alliance as a whole, it greatly helped in building the Alliance”, “the action reached its target group and has gathered interest and involvement from an good sized group of relevant stakeholders”, “the action managed to raise excellence [...] both from an academic point of view as well as regarding management and procedural methods (e.g. project management)”. Not only the benefits have been high, but the action did not represent an overwhelming cost for EELISA.

As Figure 7 shows, all actions under this ITM2 managed to initiate good transformations, helped in building the Alliance and raised excellence. The actions reached its target group and gathered a good level of involvement of relevant stakeholders. Regarding costs, the building and launching of the EINP took more efforts compared to the other actions of the ITM: as highlighted above, the initial building of the data base, the definition of the algorithm and the IT implementation took important resources.

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Figure 7: Costs and benefits graph of actions under ITM2 - Strengthening human capital, enabling balanced brain circulation and gender balance

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3.2.3 ITM3 Sharing infrastructures and other resources

ITM3 Sharing infrastructures and other resources

Two actions have been assessed under ITM3: the **EELISA catalogue of facilities** (action 8) and the production of three interlinked deliverables (action 9): **coordination of infrastructures strategy, definition of a roadmap on research infrastructures and definition of the framework conditions for joint infrastructures**. The main benefits brought by the two actions have been bringing new learning opportunities via the exchange of best practices (action 9), and a **greater visibility of the infrastructures, equipment and facilities of EELISA institutions**. Importantly, the work done under these actions might bring **substantial benefits in the long term: access to new infrastructures for our researchers, a better exploitation of resources by both an increased use of equipment and by avoiding duplication, a better budget planning for infrastructures, or a harmonization and Europeanisation of regulations and practices**. However, these benefits remain potential long-term benefits and have not been fully realized due to the short-term nature of InnoCORE. At the same time, the production and maintenance of the catalogue entailed and will require important costs (“the catalogue needs updates, administration and resources to be useful”).

Scoring benefits and costs

Building the catalogue of facilities has been the EELISA InnoCORE action with the highest level of cost according to partners. The action run with some difficulties, generated a heavy workload sometimes difficult to manage. Most importantly, “the risks associated with the action were important, materialized and somehow diminished the benefits of the action”. Indeed, EELISA partners decided to build a dedicated web platform for the infrastructure catalogue, including a log-in function allowing researchers to upload their infrastructures and equipment, and a booking contact form. The full implementation of this IT tool is still facing important difficulties, all of them related to IT issues.

Figure 8: Costs and benefits graph of actions under ITM3 Sharing infrastructures and other resources

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3.2.4 ITM4 Reinforcing cooperation with non-academic actors, especially academia-business cooperation, with targeted actions aimed to put our innovations in the market

IMT4 Reinforcing cooperation with non-academic actors, especially academia-business cooperation, with targeted actions aimed to put our innovations in the market

Two actions relate specifically with the topic of reinforcing cooperation with industry: action 10) production of the plan for **collaborative RDI, technology transfer and innovation ecosystem**, science park model and the recommendations for novel structures for governance (on the one hand) and the launching of the **EELISA 1st Industrial Chair** (action 11). Both actions had as **main benefit the quick acquisition of new skills and expertise in managing academia-industry partnerships—including legal, financial and operational aspects—thanks to peer-learning from more consolidated schemes**. As it happens with action 9, these actions, in particular the protocol for the setting up of EELISA Industrial Chairs sets the foundations for **adopting standardized processes**, therefore for the “harmonisation and Europeanisation of regulations and practices”. Agreeing on the protocol proved time- and resource-consuming: “Navigating the initial setup of collaboration may required significant time and effort, including aligning objectives, managing intellectual property rights”.

In addition to this, three other actions have been analyzed under this ITM aimed to **put innovations into the market: sharing and opening already existing activities** (action 12), the **EELISA Entrepreneurship School** (action 13) and the **Next Level competition** (action 14). The three actions have brought clear benefits to EELISA researchers and innovators, our administrative staff and our institutions, particularly in terms of **increased number of opportunities**: opportunity to access **courses and resources not available at the host institution enriching the entrepreneurial offer of our institutions**, increased networking opportunities with the formation of valuable professional connections as a result—e.g. a group of young EELISA entrepreneurs has been born out of action 12—, **increased success opportunities** (e.g. thanks to the opportunity to **validate and refine business concepts or to access the needed funds to scale up and meet investors** via the Next Level competition). Similarly to other actions, these three actions brought new learning opportunities for our administrative staff, both in terms of acquiring new skills, and also as a way of finding inspiration for the improvement of existing services or for putting in place new offers.

Important to note that the aforementioned short-term benefits should catalyze in long-term benefits not only for our institutions but for society as a whole and for the European Union: to have **more successful startups and innovations**; contribution **to economic growth and job creation** through successful entrepreneurship; contribution to the achievement of EU goals related to economic growth, job creation and innovation; strengthening European identity and cohesion through shared entrepreneurial experiences and successes.

Regarding costs, the organization of the actions had obvious associated costs: human resources needed for the organization of the activities and competitions, administrative expenses related to managing applications, reviewing submission and coordinating judging panels, venue rental in some cases, promotion of the events, travel stipends and accommodation costs for attending onsite activities. In addition to this, it is worth noting the costs of **translating material into English, particularly for action 11**, since these were already existing activities at our partners HEIs **given in the language of the hosting organization before its opening to EELISA**. The side effect of creating **false expectations** is also worth considering as an intangible cost (also existing for other actions), e.g. in these cases, not having enough funds to cover travel expenses for the participation in all activities.

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Scoring benefits and costs

As figure Figure 9 shows, the three actions aimed to put innovations into the market (i.e. actions on entrepreneurship) brought very good benefits for the Alliance and its partner institutions, particularly the Next level competition and the opening of activities to the whole Alliance. The three actions greatly helped in building the Alliance, reached their target group and managed to raise excellence. At the same time, the actions run smoothly and had commensurate costs.

The actions focused on academia-business cooperation seem not to have reached its full potential. The protocol for the creation of industrial chairs has been piloted and EELISA InnoCORE nominated its first industrial chair in December 2023. However, the whole concept needs more testing and more time to bring all its potential benefits.

Figure 9: Costs and benefits graph of actions under ITM4 Reinforcing cooperation with no-academic actors, especially academia-business cooperation, with targeted actions aimed to put our innovations in the market

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3.2.5 ITM5 Mainstreaming of comprehensive Open Science practices

ITM5 Mainstreaming of comprehensive Open Science practices

EELISA InnoCORE put in place a whole array of actions regarding the mainstreaming of open science that, for the sake of this exercise, we grouped in three actions. The production and use of the **OS methodological toolkit** and the **OS Strategic Planning and Implementation Guide** and the update of our **OS institutional policies and actions plans** have been grouped in action 15. The two other actions assessed are the **network of Open Science Ambassadors** (action 16) and the **distributed OS training hub** (action 17). Similarly to other actions (particularly, 7, 12, 13 and 14), the activities performed under this ITM led to the creation of a **community of practice, triggering new collaborations and offering new learning opportunities**, both for researchers and innovators as well as for the administrative staff. Having a joint catalogue of courses does not only mean being able to enrich the existing offer at our HEIs, but also achieve a better exploitation of resources and, in the long run, a better use of public moneys. The **update of the open science plans** needed by the WP is considered a clear benefit for the institutions achieved via action 15.

It is worth noting that the work done under ITM5 represents a clear **step forward to achieve certain medium-term goals at EU level**: actions 15, 16 and 17 meant a push in integration of open science into the strategic planning of EELISA institutions, a push in increasing OS awareness and in establishing a culture of open science within our institutions and among researchers, and a step forward in the **alignment of open science practices**, therefore supporting the EU's vision for a **unified research area** and a **cultural change towards more transparent research practices**.

Regarding costs, in addition to the obvious costs needed for the implementation of the actions (setting up the tools, production of reports but also costs linked to their communication), EELISA partners point out to the **extra workload** that these actions entailed for some members of the staff, potentially due to institutions not having still enough people to work and be fully dedicated to open science. It is also worth pointing out to the long-term costs that these actions will represent and that touch upon very different aspects, from investments in infrastructure and technologies, necessity to continually adapt to new trends and to evolving OS policies and technologies, or need to hire dedicated and specialised staff.

Scoring benefits and costs

In connection with the general parameters used for the scoring (see figure Figure 10), the guidelines produced and the update of our open science action plans (action 15) have brought the desired benefits: managed to initiate some good transformations, helped in building the Alliance, help raise excellence within the institution and/or for the Alliance, all this with a fair level of costs. The action run smoothly, and the workload generated by the action was, in general, important but not disproportionate.

The networking of open science ambassadors (action 16) and the open science training hub (action 17) seem to have had a lower impact in building the Alliance. This might be due to a question of time and maturity: the training hub has just been launched and partners have just started populating the catalogue and organizing courses. Therefore, this tool has not yet achieved its needed level of maturity. Regarding the network of OS Ambassadors, despite its potential, EELISA partners will need to analyze why the action seems not to have put down roots.

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Figure 10: Costs and benefits graph of actions under ITM5 Mainstreaming of comprehensive Open Science practices

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3.2.6 ITM6 Involvement of citizens, civil society and public/cities authorities in research and innovation

ITM6 Involvement of citizens, civil society and public/cities authorities in research and innovation

One of the main actions to achieve transformations under ITM6 was the organisation of **innovation talks** (action 18), which brought as main benefits a greater visibility of their research and innovation activities for our researchers (bringing science closer to society), as well as a greater visibility of both our individual institutions, EELISA and the European Union as a whole.

The other action assessed under ITM6 is the organisation of the two editions of the **EELISA Prototype Contest** (action 19), which brought very important benefits for EELISA, including new opportunities for innovators for testing their prototypes and putting their products into the market, new training opportunities and improved skills for both researchers and innovators and administrative staff, or the **possibility of offering access to services and infrastructures (JOSEPHS innovation lab) that would not have been possible without EELISA**. Most importantly, **citizens had the opportunity to participate in innovation processes and in the design of products and services**. Regarding costs, the only specificity pointed out in this action is the cost, or better the risk, that the action might represent regarding intellectual property if prototypes are not adequately protected (this risk did not materialize).

Scoring benefits and costs

As shown in Figure 11, the scores given to the prototype contest are aligned with the other three actions linked to it regarding putting innovations into the market under ITM5 (such as the EELISA Entrepreneurship School). Indeed, most actions linked to innovation and entrepreneurship had a very good impact in building the Alliance and raising excellence, while having commensurate costs and a manageable level of risks.

The innovation talks seem to have brought a lower level of benefit for the Alliance. Due to the high volume of events going on, attracting audience is proving more and more complicated. At the same time, the organisation of any event consumes a high level of resources. These can be reasons that explain the lower level of impact achieved by action 18.

Figure 11: Costs and benefits graph of actions under ITM6 Involvement of citizens, civil society and public/cities authorities in research and innovation

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3.2.7 ITM7 – Exploring joint structures across the European Universities

IMT7 – Exploring joint structures among Alliances

The last action assessed (action 20), **participation in FOREU meetings and activities**, generated the expected benefits and impact. Thanks to action 20, EELISA could benefit from mutual-learning opportunities that helped the Alliance build its tools and actions — **FOREU has been indeed a source of inspiration**. The participation in FOREU has also helped EELISA build itself, by having a joint voice in fora, and its function of serving as a structured and unified way of communication with DG RTD.

Scoring benefits and costs

Within this context, EELISA InnoCORE partners rated the participation in FOREU2 activities as having a good impact in building the Alliance, initiating transformation and kick-start a processes of raising excellence. The action also reached its targeted audience, and its costs were fair. No particular risks materialised and the workload was commensurate.

Figure 12: Costs and benefits graph of actions under ITM7 – Exploring joint structures across the European Universities

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4 Recommendations for the improvement of EELISA InnoCORE actions

As pointed out in the introduction “assessing the impact and costs of actions is essential for the future of EELISA. European University Having a thorough evaluation of actions will ease taking the right decisions for the long-term vision of our Alliance. The analysis performed herein tries to answer some fundamental questions for the continuation of the R&I dimension of EELISA: which actions had a very good impact and might be worth continuing, which actions were very successful but took important resources, which actions had a more limited impact and should be reviewed”.

In order to guide the future decisions of EELISA, this document ends with a set of recommendations aimed to implement the needed changes and take the right decision so that all EELISA InnoCORE actions are placed in the right-up quadrant.

Figure 13: Costs and benefits graph of actions – Describing actions and measures to be taken

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Actions with high impact, whose costs should be optimised

Action	Recommendations for improvement
1) Mapping of strategic research areas of all the members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Creating an agenda more aligned with ERA and calls-priorities of European Commission. - Considering the strengths of EELISA partners in their research fields, timely and relevant announcement of calls to researchers on the network platform (EINP).
3) Organization of symposia with representatives of R&I structures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Instead of organizing a separate symposium, the symposia can be embedded in research activities and events already carried out by partners. - Online meeting environments can be created, and symposia can be organized online. - Outputs from the symposia could be better be communicated with the participants and the society through multichannel dissemination.
4) EELISA InnoCORE Networking Platform (EINP) (WP5)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Creating an agenda for reinforced communication of the tool both at EELISA level and at single partner level. - Aligning the use of the platform with other initiatives to incentivize its use (e.g. open calls). - Creating a special page and pattern for PHD students. - Updating the criteria and the label that characterize research projects and ideas. - Create events (online sessions) to update search clusters and possible search combinations. - Disseminate the platform also in events of individual institutions not necessarily related to InnoCORE (e.g. research conferences).

Actions to be subject to a thorough assessment in terms of C&B

Action	Recommendations for improvement
8) EELISA Catalogue of facilities (portfolio of infrastructures and equipment and IT implementation of the catalogue) (D4.1 and D4.3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The EELISA Catalogue facilities faced some IT issues which caused a delay in the correct implementation. The integration of this tool within the EELISA IT tools will fix the issue. Plus, it is planned to foster the use of this catalogue within the WP9 in EELISA 2.0. The recommendation will be to use the channel of the WP9 to update the catalogue of facilities and to see how this catalogue can be a tool from promoting researchers' mobility.

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<p>9) Coordinate infrastructure strategy (D4.4) and definition of a roadmap on research infrastructures (D2.4) and definition of the framework conditions for joint infrastructures (D4.5)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - These tasks will require a concrete following. It will be proposed to keep working on it within EELISA WP9. This action also relies on the full implementation of the EELISA catalogue facilities. Once the catalogue is fully operational, a new tool to move forward to the coordination of infrastructure strategy will be proposed. The recommendation will be to set up a workshop on this subject and to follow closely the roadmap on research infrastructures.
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Actions to be improved in terms of impact

Action	Recommendations for improvement
<p>2) Portfolio of the potential of challenges revealed in first EELISA Communities with identification of scientific and technological needs (D2.5)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ensuring funding sustainability to communities. - Increasing the number of research-innovation contact people in the communities and, if possible, close communication with the policy liaison board. - Providing communities with more information about the networking platform and constantly updating this information. Thus, bringing more project ideas that naturally identify scientific and technological needs from the communities to the platform. - Bridging communities and creating a collaborative climate for shared or similar challenges in a synergistic manner.
<p>10) Production and use of the following documents: Plan for collaborative RDI, technology transfer and innovation ecosystems (D6.2), Science Park model (D6.1) and recommendations for novel structures for governance: academic and industrial participation (D6.3)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stakeholder engagement and collaboration: foster stronger collaboration between academia, industry, and relevant stakeholders through regular meetings, workshops, and forums to exchange ideas, share best practices, and identify common goals. Encourage active participation from all stakeholders in the planning and implementation of collaborative RDI projects. This ensures that the projects are aligned with the needs and priorities of all parties involved. - Enhanced communication and outreach: improve communication strategies to raise awareness about the EELISA InnoCORE project and its deliverables. - Capacity building and training: provide training programs and capacity-building initiatives to enhance the skills and capabilities of researchers, innovators, and industry professionals. Offer support and resources to facilitate technology transfer and commercialization processes, including intellectual property management and business development assistance.

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Incentive mechanisms: develop incentive mechanisms (funding opportunities, recognition programs, etc.) to encourage active participation and engagement from academia and industry. Explore alternative funding sources and partnerships to support the sustainability of the project and its activities in the long term. - Regular monitoring and evaluation: establish a robust monitoring and evaluation framework to track the progress and impact of the activities over time. Collect feedback from stakeholders regularly to identify any challenges or bottlenecks and make necessary adjustments to improve effectiveness.
<p>11) 1st EELISA Industrial Chair (MS6, WP6)</p>	<p>The position of the 1st EELISA Industrial Chair has just recently been established, and his activity is just at the beginning of his 2-year activity period, resulting in the current low-impact state. By completing the planned activities a shift towards the direction of high impact will be inherently achieved.</p> <p>Transitioning from a low impact to a high impact state for the 1st EELISA Industrial Chair requires a strategic approach and consistent effort over time.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - During the initial establishment phase (early stage), focus on laying down the groundwork for the Industrial Chair's activities. Hold introductory events and workshops to raise awareness about the Industrial Chair and its potential benefits among stakeholders, including industry partners, academic institutions, and relevant organizations. - Continuous improvement and adaptation: regularly review and assess the effectiveness of the Industrial Chair's activities, identifying areas for improvement and adjustment as needed.
<p>16) Network of Open Science Ambassadors (D3.6, task 3.5)</p>	<p>These two tasks materialized in product-type results, respectively a Network made up of 9 OS Ambassadors and an IT Platform with a Catalog of courses.</p>
<p>17) Innovative Distributed OS training Hub (D3.4, task 3.3)</p>	<p>Both products are functional and can be used. Their impact cannot yet be estimated on a large scale because within the project these physical deliverables were completed at the end of quarter III of 2023 (the first round of selection for Ambassadors) and at the end of quarter 1 and the beginning of quarter 2 of 2024 (the Platform and Catalog). This is how WP3 was projected because the Common Framework for the OS had to be developed in advance, which was the basis for the creation of these products.</p> <p>The ambassadors each carried out an exercise containing an Action Outline, so they have already adjusted to the types of actions that should be carried out and the platform can be</p>

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	<p>updated in real time. Practically, these products can work independently at the level of the Alliance. It would also be useful to use both results in EELISA 2.0 to integrate into a common platform or to spread the OS with the help of the Ambassadors network, as future actions within WP9 in EELISA 2.0</p>
<p>18) EELISA Innovation Talks (WP7)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Make it mandatory that an EELISA Innovation Talk has to be set up in such a way that it will be attended by at least 50-100 people. - Just have 4 EELISA Innovation Talks per year instead of 11. - Involve external partners such as SIEMENS (which worked very well for the second EELISA Innovation Talk at FAU). - Allocate a specific budget for the organization of each EELISA Innovation Talk that will only be fully paid if a certain threshold of visitors has been passed. - Engage professional moderators and event organizers.

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Annex I – Template used for the identification and description of costs and benefits

	Short-term: benefits within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term	Short-term: costs within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term
Researchers & innovators				
Administrative staff				
The institution				
Society, broader community				
ERA and European Union				

Annex II – Identifying costs and benefits: whole input gathered from partners

ITM1 Developing a common research and innovation agenda and action plan

1) Mapping of strategic research areas of all the members (D2.1)

	Benefit (positive outcomes and negative outcomes avoided)		Cost (resources expended, both financial and non-financial, and negative outcomes)	
	Short-term: benefits within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term	Short-term: costs within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term (<i>some costs indicated should be construed more as risks that could materialize</i>)
Researchers & innovators	<p>The set of common SRAs provides researchers with a more structured collaboration framework, provision of a common EELISA “language”, “common EELISA categories” of research areas to frame newly set collaborations.</p> <p>SRAs are linked to SDGs, the contribution of EELISA to SDGs can be traced by iterating the same methodology.</p> <p>Researchers have the opportunity to get to know each other’s research fields.</p>	<p>The use of SRAs will help understanding which SRAs have been more successful within EELISA, i.e. in which area EELISA researchers are collaborating more. This knowledge can guide future collaborations.</p> <p>SRAs are linked to SDGs, the contribution of EELISA to SDGs can be traced by iterating the same methodology.</p> <p>Development of targeted researcher support programs with a strategic perspective.</p> <p>Researchers will have the opportunity to get to know each other and build connections.</p> <p>Cumulate resources in strategic fields, strengthening joint potentials.</p>	<p>Time spent learning a new terminology.</p> <p>Terminology only valid for EELISA whereas networks of researchers are much wider.</p> <p>Possible misalignment/mismatch with small research clusters that are not seen to be recognized</p>	<p>Efforts of researchers in applying the mapping methodology for future iterations can bring costs. Alignment with European Commission’s strategic areas will require constant effort.</p> <p>Imbalances among research fields may be increased (popular – strategic – fields get more focus; special and/or unique fields may get out of scope).</p>
Administrative staff	<p>The mapping gave an overview of SRAs and capacities at all EELISA partners.</p>	<p>Better identification of critical mass per SRAs.</p>	<p>Time spent learning a new terminology.</p> <p>It was not easily practicable to really use the SRAs in a meaningful way.</p>	<p>Updates might be needed.</p>
The institution	<p>Better knowledge of the capacities of EELISA peers and better knowledge of both already going and potential collaborations.</p> <p>Common EELISA “language”, “common EELISA categories” of research areas to frame their newly set collaborations.</p> <p>Targeted allocation of EELISA’s resources to high-priority areas.</p>	<p>The strategy D2.1 provided EELISA partners with a baseline to keep working on. The strategy will have to be refined and decisions taken in the second phase. D2.1 provides a baseline to work on.</p> <p>In the medium and long term, the use of SRAs will help understanding which SRAs have been more successful within EELISA, i.e. in which area EELISA researchers are collaborating more. This knowledge can guide future decisions.</p>	<p>Important efforts spent for a somehow limited use of the mapping of capacities performed.</p> <p>Data collection requires time and effort of the institutions’ staff and researchers.</p> <p>Subscription to the database resources such as Scival may bring new costs.</p>	<p>Usage of publication and patent databases in iteration of the mapping for outcomes may require subscription fees.</p> <p>Regular, systematic update and maintaining of the database/map are required, using extensive efforts.</p>

		<p>Each institution can track the changes in their performance by their involvement in EELISA through iterations of the methodology.</p> <p>Performance assessment results can be input for the strategic re-orientation of institutions in the research field.</p>	In lack of “automatized”, developed data collection system, it requires significant resources.	
Society, broader community		<p>Unified research collaborations help conduct more precise research. Society benefits from this.</p> <p>Better allocation of resources for addressing societal challenges</p>		
ERA and European Union	<p>Better knowledge of the capacities and of the existing collaborations going on between European HEIs.</p> <p>Better knowledge of the areas of strength and weaknesses of European HEIs.</p> <p>Better alignment with ERA and EU funding schemes</p>	<p>European Union R&I framework and sustainable development goals have considered to determine the SRAs, thus, they will strengthen the ERA and tackle societal challenges.</p> <p>International competitiveness increased.</p>		

2) Portfolio of the potential of challenges revealed in first EELISA Communities with identification of scientific and technological needs (D2.5)

	Benefit (positive outcomes and negative outcomes avoided)		Cost (resources expended, both financial and non-financial, and negative outcomes)	
	Short-term: benefits within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term	Short-term: costs within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term (<i>some costs indicated should be construed more as risks that could materialize</i>)
Researchers & innovators	<p>Better environment for research and collaboration with adapted tools and resources.</p> <p>Access to external funding through joint project proposals developed by Community members (e.g., Circular EELISA Community's application to Horizon Europe fund)</p> <p>Researchers will have the opportunity to get to know each other's research fields, initiate joint research projects.</p>	<p>Design of relevant tools and resources for researchers to develop both research and training activities</p> <p>Researchers have the opportunity to get to know each other's research fields, initiate joint research projects.</p>	<p>Time spent in answering the survey for the production of the deliverable.</p>	<p>The communities' involvement in the updated versions of this deliverable can require organizing events and establishing information systems.</p>
Administrative staff	<p>Gained experience on research management with the feedbacks of researchers.</p>		<p>Time spent for the preparation of the survey and the deliverable.</p>	
The institution	<p>Better knowledge and insight on EELISA communities. The analysis run by D2.5 has helped understanding needs of Communities and will help shaping the new tools and resources offered to them under EELISA 2.0</p>	<p>Design of better tools and resources for researchers.</p>	<p>Time spent in producing the deliverable.</p> <p>In lack of "automatized" developed data collection system, it requires significant resources in order to assure accuracy and comprehensiveness of the portfolio list.</p>	<p>Regular, systematic update and maintaining of the database/map are required, using extensive efforts. Will require "automatic" system.</p>
Society, broader community	<p>SDGs are in focus.</p>	<p>Targeted use of resources to address societal challenges in collaboration with external stakeholders including diverse societal actors.</p> <p>SDGs are in focus.</p>		
ERA and European Union	<p>SDGs are in focus.</p>	<p>SDGs are in focus</p>		

3) Organisation of symposia with representatives of R&I structures (D2.2 and D2.4)

	Benefit (positive outcomes and negative outcomes avoided)		Cost (resources expended, both financial and non-financial, and negative outcomes)	
	Short-term: benefits within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term	Short-term: costs within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term (<i>some costs indicated should be construed more as risks that could materialize</i>)
Researchers & innovators	<p>Increased networking opportunities for EELISA structures: the symposia gave the opportunity to EELISA structures/units (entrepreneurship support units and OPIs in the 1st symposium, TTOs and doctoral schools in the 2nd symposium), to meet with peers and explore collaboration opportunities.</p> <p>Increased number of opportunities for researches and innovators: as an outcome of the symposia, EELISA has put in place initiatives that boosted opportunities for researchers and innovators (protocol of industrial chairs, Entrepreneurship action plan).</p> <p>Reinforced collaboration among EELISA structures, creation of new shared resources and instruments. The 1st symposium put the seed for the future Policy Liaisons Board.</p>	<p>Increased number of opportunities for researches and innovators: as an outcome of the symposia, EELISA has put in place initiatives that boosted opportunities for researchers and innovators (protocol of industrial chairs, Entrepreneurship action plan).</p>	<p>Time spent in preparing and participating in the symposium.</p> <p>Time spent in preparing the report of the symposium.</p>	<p>Sustainability of such organizations will require additional resources in the future</p>
Administrative staff	<p>Increased networking opportunities for EELISA structures: the symposia gave the opportunity to EELISA structures to meet with peers and explore opportunities.</p> <p>Reinforced collaboration among EELISA structures (entrepreneurship support units and research support office in the 1st symposium, TTOs and doctoral schools in the 2nd symposium)</p>	<p>Long term collaborations were established between the participants of the workshop.</p>	<p>Time spent in preparing and participating in the symposium.</p>	<p>Overwork for TTOs and other staff</p>
The institution	<p>Increased visibility for the institution at international level: the symposia were promoted via different means, giving</p>	<p>Better exploitation of individual resources by finding synergies and avoiding</p>	<p>Time spent in preparing and participating in the symposium.</p>	<p>Sustainability of such organizations will require additional resources in the future</p>

	EELISA partners' a platform for increased visibility.	duplication: getting to know better what other EELISA partners have (e.g. in entrepreneurship) will avoid duplication of services (when services are fully open to all EELISA partners)		
Society, broader community		Participation of industrial actors in the symposium paved the way for long-term collaboration.		
ERA and European Union	Reinforced collaboration among European HEIs.	Reinforced collaboration among European HEIs. Such collaborations will result in 'learning organizations' at EELISA level through the harmonization of research structures and the development of joint processes.		

ITM2 Strengthening human capital, enabling balanced brain circulation and gender balance

4) EELISA InnoCORE Networking Platform (EINP)

	Benefit (positive outcomes and negative outcomes avoided)		Cost (resources expended, both financial and non-financial, and negative outcomes)	
	Short-term: benefits within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term	Short-term: costs within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term (<i>some costs indicated should be construed more as risks that could materialize</i>)
Researchers & innovators	<p>Increased number of opportunities for networking and for finding new collaboration opportunities among peers, particularly for young researchers.</p> <p>Increased visibility for the research activities of the group or the researchers.</p> <p>Research collaborations are being initiated.</p> <p>Increased research groups that can manage seminar, meeting and discuss research ideas.</p>	<p>Increased number of opportunities for networking and for finding new collaboration opportunities among peers.</p> <p>Increased visibility for the research activities of the group or the researchers.</p> <p>Boost in number of joint research proposals.</p> <p>Increased research projects in collaboration within the Alliance.</p> <p>Increased manuscripts in collaboration within the Alliance.</p>	<p>Time spent in uploading research ideas.</p> <p>Initial building of the database is demanding.</p> <p>Costs in terms of missed opportunities in case of poor platform communication among academic staff.</p>	<p>Regular and systematic maintenance of the database.</p> <p>Possible dropping of tool due to non-use</p> <p>Resources (human, time) in maintaining and communicating the tools within the Alliance and each single institution.</p> <p>Costs in terms of missed opportunities in case of poor platform communication within each institution.</p>
Administrative staff	<p>Easier identification of links and possible connection among institutions.</p>	<p>Easier identification of expertise within the Alliance.</p>	<p>Administrative staff are unable to sign up the platform, making it difficult to track the progress within the research ecosystem and support researchers.</p> <p>Resources (human, time) in communicating the tools within the Alliance and each single institution.</p> <p>Resources (human, time) in the development of the platform and the production of the platform.</p>	<p>Regular and systematic maintenance of the database.</p> <p>Resources (human, time) in maintaining and communicating the tools within the Alliance and each single institution.</p>
The institution	<p>Increased visibility for the institution's researchers and research structures.</p> <p>Facilitation of exchanges among researchers.</p>	<p>Increased visibility for the institution's researchers and research structures.</p> <p>Possible networking of researchers and cluster of research ideas and projects.</p>	<p>Time and resources spent in the development of the platform.</p> <p>Resources (human, time) in communicating the tools within the Alliance and each single institution.</p>	<p>Additional costs will incur for harmonization with other EELISA IT ecosystem elements, apart from need for ensuring the sustainability of the platform.</p>

		More visibility of each institution in terms of identified research clusters and networks.	Resources (human, time) in the development of the platform and the production of the platform. Costs in terms of missed opportunities in case of poor platform communication within each institution.	Regular and systematic maintenance of the database. Resources (human, time) in maintaining and communicating the tools within the Alliance and each single institution. Possible dropping of tool due to non-use Costs in terms of missed opportunities in case of poor platform communication within each institution.
Society, broader community	Initiation of research groups committed to solution of societal and global challenges. Easier identification of expertise to face societal challenge for local community.	Solutions for various global challenges. Easier identification of expertise to face societal challenge for local community.	Few collaborations triggered with a poor recognition by communities on research advances in the alliance. <i>(This is a risk, rather than a cost, that did not materialize)</i>	Few collaborations triggered with a poor recognition by communities on research advances in the alliance.
ERA and European Union	Increased collaboration among European researchers.	Increased visibility of European research activities. Increased international competitiveness of ERA.	Few collaborations triggered with a poor recognition by communities on research advances in the alliance.	Few collaborations triggered with a poor recognition by communities on research advances in the alliance.

5) EELISA Connect open call for workshops

	Benefit (positive outcomes and negative outcomes avoided)		Cost (resources expended, both financial and non-financial, and negative outcomes)	
	Short-term: benefits within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term	Short-term: costs within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term (<i>some costs indicated should be construed more as risks that could materialize</i>)
Researchers & innovators	<p>Increased number of opportunities for networking and for finding new collaboration opportunities among peers, particularly for young researchers.</p> <p>Increased visibility for their research activities.</p> <p>New funding opportunities to organise activities.</p> <p>New opportunities to travel and visit infrastructures and facilities from other EELISA partners.</p> <p>Increased opportunities to find partners for EU project proposals.</p> <p>Increased sense of belonging to EELISA University.</p>	<p>Increased number of opportunities for networking and for finding new collaboration opportunities among peers, particularly for young researchers.</p> <p>Increased visibility for their research activities.</p> <p>New funding opportunities to organise activities.</p> <p>New opportunities to travel and visit infrastructures and facilities from other EELISA partners.</p> <p>Increased opportunities to find partners for EU project proposals.</p> <p>Increased sense of belonging to EELISA University.</p>	<p>Time and resources spent in the preparation of the proposal.</p> <p>Time and resources spent in the organisation of the workshop.</p> <p>Time and resources spent due to the complexity of the call and the management of the workshops.</p>	<p>No re-edition of the calls.</p> <p>Same researchers participate to the workshops so same researchers are benefiting from this opportunity.</p>
Administrative staff	<p>Something positive to offer for researchers in EELISA InnoCORE</p>	<p>Increased sense of belonging to EELISA University, considering the better knowledge of the possibility in terms of supporting research groups.</p>	<p>Time and resources spent in the preparation of the call and in the preparation of proposals.</p> <p>Time and resources spent in the organisation of the workshop.</p>	<p>Resources (human, time) in the development of a better management of the initiatives.</p>
The institution	<p>Increased visibility for the institution's researchers and research structures. New funding opportunities to organise activities for the institution's researchers.</p> <p>Increased visibility of infrastructures and facilities, particularly of the hosting institutions</p>	<p>Possible networking of researchers and cluster of research ideas and projects.</p> <p>More visibility of each institution in terms of identified research clusters and networks.</p>	<p>No re-edition of the calls (risk).</p> <p>Costs in terms of missed opportunities in case of poor initiatives communication within each institution.</p>	<p>No new collaborations triggered.</p> <p>No re-edition of the calls.</p>

Society, broader community	Easier identification of expertise to face societal challenges for society and community.	Easier identification of expertise to face societal challenges for society and community.	Few collaborations triggered with a poor recognition by communities on research advances in the alliance	Few collaborations triggered with a poor recognition by communities on research advances in the alliance
ERA and European Union	Increased collaboration among European researchers.	Easier identification of expertise for the EU or specific issue and research.		No new collaborations triggered. (This "cost" is low since the risk is low")

6) EELISA Gender and Diversity Work Group

	Benefit (positive outcomes and negative outcomes avoided)		Cost (resources expended, both financial and non-financial, and negative outcomes)	
	Short-term: benefits within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term	Short-term: costs within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term (<i>some costs indicated should be construed more as risks that could materialize</i>)
Researchers & innovators	<p>Increased networking opportunities.</p> <p>Increased visibility for their initiatives and also for their research (the events organised provided a platform to showcase research projects, individual activities, lectures, etc.).</p> <p>Gain new skills and knowledge via the trainings organised (Gender in Research workshop).</p>	<p>Creation of a community of practice of both formal structures (gender equality and diversity units) and informal (researchers having participated in activities)</p>	<p>Time and resources spent in the participation in the activities</p>	
Administrative staff	<p>Gender Equality Units: Increased opportunities for exchanges of good practices and exchange of knowledge, by the creation of a community of practice.</p> <p>Gender Equality Units: Better understanding of the situation of the institution of origin compared to peers (EELISA partners) (Gender Equality Plan).</p> <p>Gender Equality Units: better insight and knowledge to guide future Gender Equality Plans.</p> <p>Gender Equality Units: gain new skills and knowledge via the trainings organised (workshop on sex-harassment protocols or gender equality plans).</p>	<p>Creation of a community of practice of both formal structures (gender equality and diversity units) and informal (researchers having participated in activities)</p> <p>Gender Equality Units: better insight and knowledge to guide future Gender Equality Plans.</p>	<p>Time and resources spent in the participation in the activities</p> <p>Time and resources spent in the collection of sex-disaggregated data.</p> <p>Resources allocated for the establishment of gender and diversity policies.</p> <p>Administrative burden of implementing and monitoring new practices.</p>	<p>Regular updates and training to ensure compliance with gender and diversity policies.</p> <p>Need to address systemic biases and implement structural changes, which could be resource-intensive.</p> <p>Dedicated time to address the issues</p>
The institution	<p>Better understanding of the situation of the institution compared to peers (EELISA partners) (Gender Equality Plan).</p> <p>Better insight and knowledge to guide future Gender Equality Plans.</p>	<p>Better insight and knowledge to guide future Gender Equality Plans.</p> <p>Baseline to evaluate performance of activities both at EELISA and individual level: the Gender Equality Plan, particularly the sex-disaggregated data gathered, provide</p>	<p>Time and resources spent in the participation in the activities</p> <p>Time and resources spent in the collection of sex-disaggregated data.</p> <p>Investment in training and development programs for gender equality and diversity.</p>	<p>The GEP is not updated being just a snapshot and, therefore, not being a tool for measuring performance and change.</p> <p>Institutional reforms to address gender and diversity imbalances in staffing and leadership roles.</p>

	<p>Increased visibility of the institutions thanks to the open events.</p> <p>Sharing indicators and practices, developing new eventual measures both at institution level and alliance level.</p>	<p>a picture of the situation against which evaluate change.</p> <p>More balanced representation of women in certain fields.</p> <p>Good international benchmarking tools to compare each institution in time and space.</p>	<p>Potential resistance to change requiring strategic communication efforts.</p> <p>Addressing the academic community's scepticism regarding the efficacy of diversity initiatives.</p>	<p>Established centers for inclusivity and equality in some partners such as ITU can require funding for survival.</p> <p>The GEP is considered only something to do and not a real issue to manage and to facing.</p>
Society, broader community	<p>Promotion of a broadly accepted common good principle: gender equality and diversity.</p> <p>Empowerment of women and vindication of the role of women in science.</p>	<p>Opening up minds and showcasing opportunities in science and STEM for girls.</p> <p>More balanced representation of women in certain fields.</p> <p>Reduce gender stereotypes reproduction; gender inequality and sexual and sexist violence through education of the students and staff training.</p> <p>Recognition of the role of university alliance as a tool to face the gender issue, both in terms of developing new policies and of managing institutional changes.</p>		<p>Sustained public dialogue and education to shift societal norms and perceptions about gender roles in science and innovation.</p> <p>Long-term commitment to community outreach programs to inspire a diverse future generation of researchers and innovators.</p>
ERA and European Union	<p>Contribution to ERA action 5: Promote gender equality and foster inclusiveness, taking note of the Ljubljana declaration</p>	<p>Opening up minds and showcasing opportunities in science and STEM for girls.</p> <p>More balanced representation of women in certain fields.</p> <p>Contribution to ERA action 5: Promote gender equality and foster inclusiveness, taking note of the Ljubljana declaration</p>		<p>Long-term monitoring and assessment to ensure effective implementation across member states.</p>

7) EELISA InnoCORE Policy Liaisons Board

	Benefit (positive outcomes and negative outcomes avoided)		Cost (resources expended, both financial and non-financial, and negative outcomes)	
	Short-term: benefits within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term	Short-term: costs within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term (<i>some costs indicated should be construed more as risks that could materialize</i>)
Researchers & innovators	<p>Increased number of opportunities in joining Horizon Europe proposals and other research activities (thanks to the circulation of partner searchers).</p> <p>Increased opportunities and chances to find new research partners (thanks to the network of research support offices and the circulation of information among them).</p>	<p>Increased number of opportunities in joining Horizon Europe proposals and other research activities (thanks to the circulation of partner searchers)</p> <p>Increased career development opportunities.</p>	<p>Time and resources spent in attending meetings and contributing to discussion and positions papers (where needed).</p>	
Administrative staff	<p>Increased mutual learning opportunities</p> <p>Improvement of skills, capabilities, improvement of the services provided thanks to the mutual learning exercises</p> <p>Exposure to diverse administrative practices and policies.</p> <p>Development of project management skills through collaboration on international projects.</p>	<p>Improvement of the services provided thanks to the mutual learning exercises</p> <p>Increased career development opportunities.</p> <p>Recognition of the role of the administrative staff in university alliance, with a focus on the research managers role and profile.</p>	<p>Time and resources spent in attending meetings and contributing to positions papers</p>	<p>Possible overlap with work within associations (LERU, CESAER, The Guild...)</p>
The institution	<p>Greater visibility at EU-level thanks to the publication of position papers.</p> <p>Stronger voice in EU affairs thanks to sharing views, joining forces and getting to shared opinions translated in papers.</p> <p>Improvement of the services provided</p> <p>Stronger voice in European networks and associations, as the positions are backed by an Alliance of 9 universities.</p>	<p>Stronger voice in EU affairs</p> <p>Greater visibility at EU-level</p>	<p>Time and resources spent in attending meetings and contributing to positions papers</p>	
Society, broader community	<p>Better use of public moneys via the improvement of services, skills and institutions.</p>	<p>Better use of public moneys via the improvement of services, skills and institutions.</p> <p>Policy papers may have impact on research community in Europe.</p>		<p>Possible mismatch between the needs of the institution and the alliance and the needs brought forward by the community/society</p>

ERA and European Union	<p>Visibility of EELISA InnoCORE Policy Liaisons Board within ERA and EU</p> <p>Contribution to ERA Action 17 Enhance the strategic capacity of Europe's public research performing organisations</p>	<p>Policy papers may have impact on ERA Policies and Horizon Europe Programme.</p> <p>Contribution to ERA Action 17 enhance the strategic capacity of europe's public research performing organisations</p>		
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ITM3 Sharing research infrastructures and other resources

8) EELISA Catalogue of facilities (portfolio of infrastructures and equipment and IT implementation of the catalogue) (D4.1 and D4.3)

	Benefit (positive outcomes and negative outcomes avoided)		Cost (resources expended, both financial and non-financial, and negative outcomes)	
	Short-term: benefits within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term	Short-term: costs within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term (<i>some costs indicated should be construed more as risks that could materialize</i>)
Researchers & innovators	Exchange of best practices and information about the infrastructures.	<p>Access to new and different infrastructures.</p> <p>Greater visibility for infrastructures, facilities and equipment owned by the groups.</p> <p>Better exploitation of resources (i.e. better exploitation of infrastructures by an increased use).</p> <p>Increased opportunities to find research collaborations.</p>	<p>Time spend in uploading new infrastructures in the catalogue</p> <p>Resources (human, time) in communicating the tools within the Alliance and each single institution.</p> <p>Resources (human, time) in the development of the platform and the updating of the platform.</p>	Time spend in updating new infrastructures in the catalogue and training new external users
Administrative staff	<p>New learning opportunities (infrastructure managers)</p> <p>New ways of managing infrastructures.</p>	Create a network of technicians and administrative staff experts in this field.	<p>The catalogue of facilities needs updates, administration and resources to be useful.</p> <p>Define access rules related to external user.</p> <p>Resources (human, time) in communicating the tools within the Alliance and each single institution.</p>	<p>The catalogue of facilities needs updates, administration and resources to be useful.</p> <p>Managing and supporting the external users</p>
The institution	<p>Greater visibility of the infrastructures, equipment and facilities of the institution.</p> <p>Increased exploitation of the resources of the institution.</p>	<p>Better use of resources by avoiding duplication of infrastructures and equipment.</p> <p>Full exploitation of resources.</p> <p>Foster collaboration in the research activities.</p>	<p>Time and resources spent in the creation of the catalogue.</p> <p>Limited use of the catalogue by the research community.</p>	Waste of resources used (in case the catalogue is not continued)!!!

Society, broader community	Have a feedback on the impact of funding in research infrastructures.	Better use of public funds. Effectiveness in the use of public funds for infrastructures.	Perception of fund wasting by seeing duplicated infrastructures within the network.	Opposition to the use of public resources in research infrastructures.
ERA and European Union	A better perception of the effort of the community related to the infrastructure network Contribution to ERA action 8 "Strengthen sustainability, accessibility and resilience of research infrastructures in the ERA"	Better use of public funds Contribution to ERA action 8 "Strengthen sustainability, accessibility and resilience of research infrastructures in the ERA"	Bureaucratic procedures and access to the external infrastructure too complex. Too many duplicated resources.	Reduction of the dedicated funds.

9) Coordinate infrastructure strategy (D4.4), Definition of a roadmap on research infrastructures (D2.4) and definition of the framework conditions for joint infrastructures (D4.5)

	Benefit (positive outcomes and negative outcomes avoided)		Cost (resources expended, both financial and non-financial, and negative outcomes)	
	Short-term: benefits within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term	Short-term: costs within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term (<i>some costs indicated should be construed more as risks that could materialize</i>)
Researchers & innovators	Better knowledge of admin rules. Better knowledge and overview of the European panorama in research infrastructures.	Facilitate the use of equipment and increase exchanges. Application for funding research projects more based on the ideas and on research personnel.	Overcoming barriers Lack of interest due to the complexity of the access procedures	Return to a national or local-based approach for infrastructure access
Administrative staff	Exchange of best practices, rules.	Network of administrative and technical staff that create a common protocol for accessing research infrastructures	Two different and parallel requests from the institution: "local or/and national" and European strategies for the infrastructure management.	Tightening of rules and user support, increase in bureaucracy
The institution	Better knowledge of their own infrastructure impact respect on the other partners.	A better planning of their funds in research infrastructures, to create a priority list and strategic alliances.	Low priority of European networking respect to the national or local scenario.	Concentration of resources for local and national activities Additional funds will be needed for dissemination of the activities and for maintaining the current joint infrastructures
Society, broader community	Awareness of their capability to compete on the European scenario	Benefits from social and economic point of view (impact)	Perception of poor use of public resources	Lobbying to reduce resources for research infrastructures respect to other more relevant ones.
ERA and European Union	Awareness of their capability to compete on the global scenario. Contribution to ERA action 8 "Strengthen sustainability, accessibility and resilience of research infrastructures in the ERA"	Stronger research communities that are able to tackle challenges. Harmonisation and Europeanisation of regulations and practices. Contribution to ERA action 8 "Strengthen sustainability, accessibility and resilience of research infrastructures in the ERA"	Perception of poor use of European funding for networking.	Reduction of the European funds on research infrastructures networking.

ITM4 Reinforcing cooperation with non-academic actors, especially academia-business cooperation; with targeted actions aimed to put our innovations in the market

10) Production and use of Plan for collaborative RDI, technology transfer and innovation ecosystems (D6.2), Science park model (D6.1) and recommendations for novel structures for governance: academic and industrial participation (D6.3)

	Benefit (positive outcomes and negative outcomes avoided)		Cost (resources expended, both financial and non-financial, and negative outcomes)	
	Short-term: benefits within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term	Short-term: costs within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term (<i>some costs indicated should be construed more as risks that could materialize</i>)
Researchers & innovators	<p>Access to enhanced collaborative platforms and tools, facilitating the immediate initiation of industry-relevant research projects and innovation activities.</p> <p>Streamlined processes for technology transfer contribute to quicker market application of research findings.</p>	<p>Increased number of opportunities for PhD students to do both industrial and international PhDs thesis.</p> <p>Sustained growth in industry-academia collaborations leads to an enriched research environment. Innovators gain a reputation for practical, market-ready solutions, attracting further investment and partnership opportunities.</p>		<p>Additional costs may appear due to the circulation costs of students.</p>
Administrative staff	<p>Peer-learning and opportunities to find inspiration for the improvement of existing services or for putting in place new offers.</p> <p>Quick acquisition of new skills and knowledge related to cross-border collaborations</p>		<p>Time and resources spent in providing the information needed for the production of the reports with no clear short-term impact.</p>	
The institution	<p>D6.3 includes a first version of a protocol to nominate EELISA industrial chairs: this is the bases to achieve the long-term benefit of expanding industrial chairs.</p>	<p>Opportunity to expand already existing industrial chairs and establish new industrial chairs with a strong international dimension.</p>	<p>Time and resources spent in providing the information needed for the production of the reports with no clear short-term impact.</p>	<p>The protocol for industrial chairs reveals inoperative and cannot be further used (potential). If the protocols for establishing industrial chairs prove inoperative, significant resources may have been expended without achieving the desired outcomes. Adjustments and revisions could lead to further costs. Compliance with the national higher education standards and regulations may require advocacy efforts that may lead to additional efforts and hence costs.</p>

Society, broader community		<p>Easier implication in research Better applied research, research applied to societal needs and to solve industrial challenges, thanks to a potential increase in the number of industrial PhD thesis</p> <p>A sustained increase in applied research and innovations directly addressing societal and industrial challenges contributes to economic growth, job creation, and enhanced quality of life.</p>		
ERA and European Union	Contribution to ERA action 7 “Better knowledge valorisation”	<p>Contribution to ERA action 7 “Better knowledge valorisation”</p> <p>Harmonisation and Europeanisation of regulations and practices</p>		

11) 1st EELISA Industrial Chair (WP6)

	Benefit (positive outcomes and negative outcomes avoided)		Cost (resources expended, both financial and non-financial, and negative outcomes)	
	Short-term: benefits within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term	Short-term: costs within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term (<i>some costs indicated should be construed more as risks that could materialize</i>)
Researchers & innovators	<p>New opportunities to establish new international collaborations with both peer researchers and industrial partners from other countries.</p> <p>Greater visibility to the already existing industrial chairs.</p>	<p>New opportunities to establish new international collaborations with both peer researchers and industrial partners from other countries.</p> <p>Access to industry-specific challenges and resources, enabling applied research and innovation. Enhancement of research relevance by aligning with industry needs, leading to more impactful outcomes.</p> <p>Sustained partnerships with industry can lead to ongoing research funding, commercialization of research outputs, and enhanced employability for graduates. Continuous exchange of knowledge and skills between academia and industry strengthens the innovation ecosystem.</p>	<p>Time and resources spent for start the collaboration.</p>	<p>Navigating the initial setup of collaborations may require significant time and effort, including aligning objectives, managing intellectual property rights, and establishing communication channels.</p>
Administrative staff	<p>Exposure to diverse administrative practices and policies.</p> <p>Learning from partners with more consolidated schemes. Development of expertise in managing academia-industry partnerships, including legal, financial, and operational aspects. Enhances the institution's capacity to support complex collaborative projects.</p>	<p>Development of expertise in managing academia-industry partnerships, including legal, financial, and operational aspects. Enhances the institution's capacity to support complex collaborative projects.</p>	<p>Time and resources spent for providing the needed information for the protocol.</p>	
The institution	<p>Greater visibility to the already existing industrial chairs.</p>	<p>Opportunity to expand already existing industrial chairs and establish new industrial chairs with a strong international dimension.</p> <p>Establishment of standardized processes and protocols for</p>	<p>Agreeing on the protocol for establishing EELISA industrial chairs was time-consuming due to the differences in the existing schemes at the different EELISA partners.</p>	<p>No use of the protocol, no new EELISA industrial chairs.</p> <p>Significant administrative effort required to establish and maintain industrial chairs, including negotiation of terms,</p>

		industrial collaboration, improving efficiency and scalability of future partnerships.	The contribution of the Industrial Chair model at EELISA level is yet unclear in terms of academia-industry collaboration.	compliance with regulations, and coordination between partners.
Society, broader community	Better connection and synergy between industries and university			Possible mismatch between society, university and industries in terms of incentives to collaborate.
ERA and European Union	Contribution to ERA action 7 "Better knowledge valorisation"	Contribution to ERA action 7 "Better knowledge valorisation"		

12) EELISA Co-creation and Innovation processes: sharing of and opening up activities (WP7)

	Benefit (positive outcomes and negative outcomes avoided)		Cost (resources expended, both financial and non-financial, and negative outcomes)	
	Short-term: benefits within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term	Short-term: costs within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term (<i>some costs indicated should be construed more as risks that could materialize</i>)
Researchers & innovators	<p>Increased number of training opportunities on entrepreneurship and innovation.</p> <p>Opportunity to access courses and resources not available at the host institution.</p> <p>Increased networking opportunities, which are key for starting any company.</p> <p>Opportunity to learn new innovation methods that would not have been accessible without EELISA InnoCORE.</p> <p>Possibility to get user feedback for prototypes before market access: Improved product development.</p> <p>Quick dissemination of research findings through established networks.</p> <p>Initial boost in visibility and recognition within the European research community.</p>	<p>Increased number of training opportunities on entrepreneurship and innovation.</p> <p>Opportunity to access courses and resources not available at the host institution.</p> <p>More successful startups and innovators.</p> <p>Sustained opportunities for collaboration leading to deeper and more impactful research outcomes.</p> <p>Establishment of long-lasting professional relationships with peers across Europe.</p> <p>Cumulative increase in reputation and influence in their respective fields due to continued involvement in high-profile projects.</p>	<p>Creation of false expectations (not enough funds to cover all travel expenses to cover the participation in all activities)</p> <p>Delays in communications and publications highlight the need for improved methodologies, tools, and resources to make communication more efficient among partners and with external stakeholder.</p>	<p>Overwhelming quantity of initiatives going on making it difficult to differentiate or choose.</p>
Administrative staff	<p>Peer-learning and opportunities to find inspiration for the improvement of existing services or for putting in place new offers.</p> <p>Quick acquisition of new skills and knowledge related to cross-border collaborations.</p>	<p>Improvement of existing processes.</p> <p>Development of expertise in managing complex international projects.</p>	<p>Translation of courses and training material into English.</p> <p>Time and resources needed to organize activities.</p> <p>Delays in communications and publications highlight the need for improved methodologies, tools, and resources to make communication more efficient among partners and with external stakeholder.</p>	

			It's needed to analyze the time spent versus the results achieved to decide on which activities to focus.	
The institution	<p>Opportunity to access courses and resources not available at the host institution.</p> <p>Find inspiration for the improvement of existing services or for putting in place new offers.</p> <p>Creation of a critical mass of participants from all EELISA institutions to have activities that would otherwise not have been possible.</p> <p>Initial boost in visibility and reputation as a result of participation in the project.</p> <p>Immediate access to new funding opportunities and research resources.</p> <p>Quick integration into European research networks and partnerships.</p>	<p>Opportunity to access courses and resources not available at the host institution.</p> <p>Establishment of a sustainable framework for ongoing international collaborations.</p> <p>Continuous growth of research capacity and infrastructure through shared resources.</p> <p>Long-lasting impact on the institution's competitiveness and position within the European research landscape</p>	<p>Time and resources needed to organize activities.</p> <p>Delays in communications and publications highlight the need for improved methodologies, tools, and resources to make communication more efficient among partners and with external stakeholder.</p>	Allocation of time and efforts of the existing innovation and entrepreneurship structures to EELISA E&I activities without a supporting budget.
Society, broader community	<p>Better use of public moneys. Direct access to EELISA innovations in EELISA Test Spaces.</p> <p>Quick promotion of social cohesion through cross-cultural collaboration.</p>	<p>Benefit from innovations developed in the framework of EELISA InnoCORE.</p> <p>Sustainable economic growth and development driven by ongoing innovation and knowledge transfer.</p>	Delays in communications and publications highlight the need for improved methodologies, tools, and resources to make communication more efficient among partners and with external stakeholder.	
ERA and European Union	<p>Better use of public moneys by creating synergies.</p> <p>Contribution to ERA action 14: Bring science closer to citizens</p> <p>Quick reinforcement of European identity and solidarity through joint initiatives.</p> <p>Initial increase in global competitiveness as a result of promoting European innovation.</p>	<p>Better use of public moneys by creating synergies.</p> <p>Contribution to ERA action 14: bring science closer to citizens.</p> <p>Establishment of a solid foundation for the long-term integration and coordination of European research efforts.</p> <p>Sustainable promotion of European values and leadership in global research and innovation.</p>	Delays in communications and publications highlight the need for improved methodologies, tools, and resources to make communication more efficient among partners and with external stakeholder.	

13) EELISA Entrepreneurship School (WP7)

	Benefit (positive outcomes and negative outcomes avoided)		Cost (resources expended, both financial and non-financial, and negative outcomes)	
	Short-term: benefits within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term	Short-term: costs within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term (<i>some costs indicated should be construed more as risks that could materialize</i>)
Researchers & innovators	<p>Great international learning experience for young entrepreneurs.</p> <p>Increased networking opportunities</p> <p>Exposure to a variety of entrepreneurial methodologies and innovative thinking processes. Opportunity to validate and refine business ideas in a supportive, multidisciplinary environment.</p> <p>Access to mentorship and guidance from experienced entrepreneurs.</p> <p>Immediate access to entrepreneurship education and training programs.</p> <p>Development of practical skills such as business planning, marketing, and financial management.</p> <p>Exposure to real-world business challenges and case studies.</p>	<p>The EELISA Entrepreneurship School helped its participants to gain the knowledge and skills to become successful entrepreneurs.</p> <p>Increased networking opportunities. A group of EELISA young entrepreneurs has been born out of the action. Formation of valuable professional connections and networks</p> <p>Establishment of a strong entrepreneurial mindset and skillset.</p> <p>Increased confidence and readiness to launch and grow successful ventures.</p> <p>Potential for long-term career success and financial independence.</p> <p>Contribution to economic growth and job creation through successful entrepreneurship.</p>	<p>Commitment to maintaining relevance and quality in entrepreneurship education amid evolving industry trends.</p> <p>Potential costs associated with providing support services for student entrepreneurs, such as incubation spaces and mentorship programs.</p> <p>Risks of resource constraints and competition from other institutions offering similar programs.</p> <p>Ongoing investment in faculty development, program evaluation, and continuous improvement.</p>	<p>Ongoing commitment required to maintain and leverage network relationships.</p>
Administrative staff	<p>Also, for the administrative staff the EELISA Entrepreneurship School was a great learning experience.</p> <p>Acquisition of a broader understanding of the entrepreneurial ecosystem, enriching their capacity to support university-based startups.</p> <p>Increased interest from prospective students and stakeholders due to the focus on entrepreneurship education.</p> <p>Diversification of academic offerings, attracting a wider range of students and faculty.</p>	<p>Better knowledge of entrepreneurship skills and knowledge.</p> <p>Networking effects with participants and experts who participated in the EELISA Entrepreneurship School.</p> <p>Alignment with the institution's mission of fostering creativity, innovation, and social impact.</p>	<p>Time and resources needed to organize the EELISA Entrepreneurship School.</p>	

	Opportunities for collaboration with local businesses, government agencies, and other stakeholders			
The institution	<p>The EELISA Entrepreneurship School enriched the offer of entrepreneurship activities at EELISA institutions.</p> <p>More students could profit from entrepreneurship training than would have been possible without the EELISA Entrepreneurship School</p> <p>Offer complementing the portfolio of the institution.</p>	A new format could be successfully tested that will enrich the portfolio of activities in the future.		Commitment to supporting the ongoing development of startups and entrepreneurial initiatives that emerge from the School, which may require additional financial and mentoring resources.
Society, broader community	<p>Society profits from the startups that were founded immediately after the EELISA Entrepreneurship School.</p> <p>Potential for job creation and reduced unemployment rates.</p> <p>Fostering a culture of innovation and creativity within the community.</p>	<p>Society will profit from the startups that were already founded and will be founded as a consequence of the EELISA Entrepreneurship School.</p> <p>Strengthening social ties and cohesion through collaborative entrepreneurship initiatives.</p>		
ERA and European Union	<p>Increased prestige for the EU due to funding of successful activities.</p> <p>Immediate contribution to the objectives of the European Research Area (ERA) through the promotion of entrepreneurship and innovation.</p> <p>Strengthening the European entrepreneurial ecosystem through collaboration and knowledge exchange.</p> <p>Increased visibility of European entrepreneurship on the global stage</p>	<p>Increased prestige for the EU due to funding of successful activities.</p> <p>Contribution to the achievement of EU goals related to economic growth, job creation, and innovation.</p> <p>Strengthened European identity and cohesion through shared entrepreneurial experiences and successes.</p> <p>Positioning Europe as a global leader in entrepreneurship and innovation, driving long-term prosperity and sustainability.</p>	Resources spent for the activities	

14) EELISA Start-up competition (WP7)

	Benefit (positive outcomes and negative outcomes avoided)		Cost (resources expended, both financial and non-financial, and negative outcomes)	
	Short-term: benefits within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term	Short-term: costs within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term (<i>some costs indicated should be construed more as risks that could materialize</i>)
Researchers & innovators	<p>Increased opportunities to access the needed funds to scale up and meet investors.</p> <p>New and increased networking opportunities, needed to scale up.</p> <p>Possibility to test their competitiveness on the European scenario.</p> <p>Direct feedback on business models and strategies from seasoned entrepreneurs and investors.</p>	<p>Increased opportunities to access the needed funds to scale up and meet investors.</p> <p>European-based possibility of scale-up.</p> <p>Sustainable business growth facilitated by early-stage validation and networking.</p> <p>Building relationships with mentors, investors, and advisors for ongoing support.</p> <p>Increased credibility and recognition within the startup ecosystem.</p> <p>Validation of their business concepts, helping attract further investment and talent.</p> <p>Integration into the broader startup community, leading to collaboration and growth opportunities.</p>	<p>Time and resources spent in preparing the application.</p>	<p>Focussing on the local scale</p> <p>Possible need to pivot or revise business models based on competition feedback, requiring additional investment.</p>
Administrative staff	<p>Possibility to build a network with startups and investors</p> <p>Benchmarking competition and award organization</p>	<p>Possibility to benefit from an established network of startups and investors.</p> <p>Synergy of administrative resources on this topic</p>	<p>Time and resources spent in the preparation of the call, promotion and being part of the jury.</p>	<p>Lack of participation to the events</p>
The institution	<p>Greater visibility for EELISA institutions, particularly push to visibility with external stakeholders (investors).</p> <p>Boost to EELISA incubators, greater visibility for EELISA entrepreneurship services, incubators.</p>	<p>Possibility to offer more powerful services to our innovators: access to investors and networking opportunities from not just one HEI but nine.</p> <p>Establishment of a new successful format that can be offered on a regular basis in the future.</p>	<p>All: Financial investment in organizing and hosting the competition, including venue rental, event promotion, and staff costs.</p>	<p>Prioritize local events for institutional participation</p> <p>Lack of linkages between local activities and EELISA activities</p> <p>(Lack of) Sustained financial commitment to support the</p>

	<p>Greater opportunities for start-ups incubated within the EELISA ecosystem.</p> <p>Possibility to create a critical mass of advanced startup and interest from investors by joining forces with EELISA partners! At only one EELISA institution such a successful event would not have been possible.</p> <p>Awareness about their innovation level respect to the European one.</p> <p>Enhanced reputation and visibility within the entrepreneurship ecosystem.</p> <p>Engagement and involvement of students, alumni, and community members.</p> <p>Networking opportunities with industry leaders, investors, and potential partners.</p>	<p>Increase funds and commitment on innovation.</p> <p>Potential for commercial success stories that enhance the institution's legacy and attract further investment.</p> <p>Establishment of ongoing relationships with startups, investors, and sponsors.</p> <p>Opportunities for collaboration and partnership with winning startups.</p> <p>Talent attraction and retention by positioning themselves as hubs of innovation.</p>	<p>Allocation of resources for prize funds, grants, or in-kind support for winning startups.</p> <p>Administrative expenses related to managing applications, reviewing submissions, and coordinating judging panels.</p> <p>Potential costs associated with providing travel stipends or accommodations for finalists and judges.</p> <p>Time and effort required from staff and stakeholders involved in planning and executing the competition.</p> <p>Commitment to ongoing support and follow-up for winning startups, including mentorship, access to funding, and networking opportunities</p>	<p>entrepreneurial ecosystem, including incubators and accelerators.</p>
Society, broader community	<p>Awareness about their innovation level respect to the European one.</p> <p>Exposure to innovative ideas and technologies through presentations and demos.</p> <p>Inspiration and motivation to pursue their own entrepreneurial endeavors.</p>	<p>Society will profit from the investment in successful startups.</p> <p>Increase interest in innovation that generates impact.</p> <p>Contribution to local economic development and job creation through successful startups.</p> <p>Formation of connections and partnerships that may lead to future opportunities.</p> <p>Long-lasting impact on the entrepreneurial ecosystem, fostering continued growth and innovation.</p>	<p>Lack of interest in innovation</p>	<p>Perceiving investment in innovation as unprofitable</p>
ERA and European Union	<p>Increased prestige for the EU due to funding a successful activity.</p> <p>Awareness about their innovation level</p>	<p>Increased prestige for the EU due to funding a successful activity</p> <p>Strategic and synergic use of funding and generation of a priority list for innovation funds.</p>	<p>Resources spent for the activity</p> <p>Lack of feedback about synergic role of innovation networking</p>	<p>Reduction of networking project funding activity</p> <p>Risk of creating a competitive, rather than collaborative, atmosphere among EU</p>

	<p>Engagement of stakeholders from member states, fostering collaboration and knowledge exchange.</p> <p>Showcasing Europe's vibrant startup ecosystem and its potential on the global stage.</p>	<p>Nurturing a culture of innovation and risk-taking, contributing to long-term economic competitiveness.</p> <p>Strengthening of the European Single Market by facilitating the growth and expansion of startups across borders.</p>		<p>institutions if not managed carefully.</p>
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ITM5 Mainstreaming of comprehensive Open Science practices

15) Production and use of OS Methodological Toolkit (D3.1) and OS Strategic Planning and Implementation Guide (D3.2), and Updated OS Institutional policies and actions plans (D3.3)

		Benefit (positive outcomes and negative outcomes avoided)		Cost (resources expended, both financial and non-financial, and negative outcomes)	
		Short-term: benefits within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term	Short-term: costs within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term (<i>some costs indicated should be construed more as risks that could materialize</i>)
Researchers & innovators	<p>Enhanced networking, establishment of practitioner-expert networks, and initiation of new collaborations.</p> <p>Establishing shared good practices, especially about the proper articulation between open science and valorization.</p> <p>Better understanding of institution's future plans and their impact on a researcher career.</p>	<p>Sustained collaborations and networks among researchers and innovators, potentially leading to lasting partnerships and interdisciplinary research.</p> <p>Collaborations around dedicated infrastructures for open science (eg publication database, data management) Favoured the collaboration and mobility of researchers among EELISA institutions due to policies' homogenization.</p>	<p>Time and effort from administrative staff and researchers to gather data and produce the reports, potentially diverting resources from other projects if there are not specialised units to manage open science.</p> <p>The extra workload of not having enough people to work on open science or not reaching the right people in the Alliance</p> <p>We have to remain very cautious about insertion of OS aspects within the evaluation of research framework</p>	<p>The necessity of continually adapting to evolving Open Science policies, which might require ongoing learning and adaptation of research practices. This could lead to time diverted from primary research activities to comply with Open Science standards, including data sharing and open publication requirements. Additionally, there might be a need for investments in infrastructure to store and manage open data, as well as potential publication fees associated with open access journals.</p> <p>Different legal practices linked to national open science policies, or the absence of national policies and cultural differences between institutions, can lead to difficulties in establishing and implementing common practices under EELISA.</p> <p>Overwork due to the implementations of new plans.</p>	
Administrative staff	<p>The production of the reports has created a network of practitioners and experts, new collaborations have been born out of WP3 and the connection in OS (OS EELISA community, group of librarians)</p> <p>A better understanding of the open science policies in their institutions and in another institutions.</p>	<p>Enhanced professional development through engagement with innovative research practices and policies. This involvement leads to improved administrative efficiency and effectiveness in managing research outputs and compliance with Open Science policies. Additionally, staff benefit from increased opportunities for collaboration with a broader network of experts and practitioners, fostering professional growth and contributing to the institution's strategic positioning in the research ecosystem.</p>	<p>Time allocated to collect data to produce the reports.</p> <p>The extra workload of not having enough people to work on open science or not reaching the right people in the Alliance.</p> <p>The network has to be formally extended to Libraries, which are the main service in charge of OS in the institutions.</p>	<p>Administrative staff may face ongoing resource allocations for maintaining and updating Open Science policies and practices. This includes continuous training and development to stay aligned with evolving Open Science standards, potentially requiring adjustments in institutional infrastructure and practices. Additionally, there may be a need for sustained effort in supporting researchers and innovators in complying with Open Science requirements, which could impact the administrative workload and resource distribution within institutions.</p>	

		Alignment of Open Science policies in EELISA. Favouring the collaboration and mobility with other institutions.	Time spent in creating the actions plans.	Overwork due to the implementations of new plans. Risk to duplicate with the existing training material/formation.
The institution	<p>Greater visibility thanks to the dissemination of the reports (the work of the WP3 will be showcased in an EC report on the work of Alliances).</p> <p>The update of open science plans needed by the WP has been a benefit (the institutions have been "forced" to analyse the state-of-play of OS and revisit their plans).</p>	<p>Institutional strengthening through the integration of Open Science into strategic planning, leading to enhanced research quality and compliance with European and global Open Science mandates.</p> <p>Greater visibility, perhaps through a common portal referencing open publications of EELISA.</p>	Financial resources might be allocated for the development and dissemination of the toolkit and guides, including workshops, training sessions, and the publication of materials.	<p>Ongoing commitment to maintain and update Open Science policies and practices, requiring continuous allocation of resources.</p> <p>Potential need for infrastructure development to support Open Science practices (e.g., repositories, data management tools), which could require significant financial investment. Training and development costs to ensure staff, researchers, and innovators are equipped to engage with Open Science practices effectively.</p> <p>Need to address the requirement for dedicated or specialized staff to manage and support Open Science practices effectively. This could involve hiring new personnel with expertise in Open Science methodologies or providing extensive training for existing staff to develop necessary skills. This need for specialized staff underscores the institutional commitment to Open Science, potentially leading to additional financial and organizational considerations to sustain these efforts effectively.</p> <p>Different legal practices linked to national open science policies, or the absence of national policies and cultural differences between institutions, can lead to difficulties in establishing and implementing common practices under EELISA.</p> <p>Variety of national regulations and policies is a major impediment to define a common framework of actions.</p>
Society, broader community	<p>Enhanced public access to research outputs, better utilization of public funding.</p> <p>A better understanding of the work done in the institution.</p>	<p>Better use of public research or public funding.</p> <p>More accessible scientific research.</p> <p>Societal impact through the long-term accessibility of research outputs, contributing to knowledge dissemination and education.</p>	Time spent in creating the actions plans.	<p>Any discussion of costs is more implicitly related to the resources required for implementing Open Science practices rather than explicitly detailing societal or community-level long-term costs.</p> <p>Potential increment of bureaucratic tasks.</p>

		To assess societal impact of research with a cross country point of view. Increase the participation of the society in the institution and vice versa.		
ERA and European Union	<p>Increased alignment with Open Science policies, contributing to the broader European Research Area objectives.</p> <p>Representation of the Alliance at the inter-alliance level through the creation of special interest groups such as the EELISA Librarians Group. (e.g. FOR EU LIB Group)</p> <p>Access to a collection of use cases of OS implementations</p> <p>Contribution to ERA Action 1: Enable the open sharing of knowledge and the re-use of research outputs, including through the development of the european open science cloud (EOSC)</p>	<p>ERA and European Union: Long-term alignment with ERA objectives, supporting the EU's vision for a unified research area that fosters innovation and collaboration across borders.</p> <p>To initiate cooperation activities and possible projects within the network of all European Universities by participating in networks such as FOR EU Lib Group</p> <p>Identifying legal brakes to OS in the national regulations in the frame of the Copyright Directive</p> <p>Alignment of Open Science policies in EELISA. Favouring the collaboration and mobility with other institutions</p> <p>Contribution to ERA Action 1: Enable the open sharing of knowledge and the re-use of research outputs, including through the development of the european open science cloud (EOSC)</p> <p>Contribution to ERA Action 2: Advance towards the reform the assessment system for research, researchers and institutions to improve their quality, performance and impact</p>		Typically, such costs could involve investments in infrastructure, policy development, and governance to support Open Science across member states, aligning with broader EU strategies for research and innovation.

16) Network of Open Science Ambassadors (D3.6, task 3.5)

	Benefit (positive outcomes and negative outcomes avoided)		Cost (resources expended, both financial and non-financial, and negative outcomes)	
	Short-term: benefits within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term	Short-term: costs within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term (<i>some costs indicated should be construed more as risks that could materialize</i>)
Researchers & innovators	<p>Greater visibility for OS champions from the different EELISA institutions. Exchange of best practices and peer learning.</p> <p>Access to training and resources to implement Open Science practices in current research.</p> <p>Accelerating the process of meeting the needs/expectations by collecting all requests related to Open Science at a single point and distributing them to the relevant units for resolution.</p> <p>A contact person to consult/resolve OS questions.</p>	<p>Development of a sustainable network for collaboration and innovation. Potential for greater impact and recognition of research through open access and data sharing.</p> <p>Enhanced reproducibility and transparency of research, leading to increased trust and credibility.</p> <p>The formation of an OS community.</p>	<p>Time invested in becoming OS Ambassadors and engaging with the network.</p> <p>Diversion of research time for training in Open Science principles.</p> <p>Potential disruption of established research processes to align with Open Science practices.</p> <p>Articulation with the current networks existing in the institutions</p>	<p>Continuous adaptation to evolving Open Science policies and technologies.</p> <p>Possible increased administrative responsibilities associated with Open Science compliance.</p> <p>Need for ongoing engagement in the OS community to maintain ambassador status.</p> <p>To guarantee the perennity of the network</p>
Administrative staff	<p>Greater visibility for OS champions from the different EELISA institutions.</p> <p>Exchange of best practices and peer learning.</p> <p>Greater involvement in the research process through the support of Open Science initiatives.</p> <p>Skill development in Open Science practices, policies, and tools. Building a network with other Open Science practitioners and experts.</p> <p>Facilitate their work due to having an expert to consult</p>	<p>Establishing a culture of Open Science within the institution.</p> <p>Improved efficiency in research management and policy implementation.</p> <p>A major integration of researchers, administrative staff and institution.</p>	<p>Resource allocation for the establishment and management of the OS Ambassador program.</p> <p>Administrative time spent supporting the recruitment and coordination of OS Ambassadors.</p> <p>Time required for the local coordination for the administrative staff; to avoid some additional administrative layers</p>	<p>Ongoing support for OS Ambassadors, potentially requiring dedicated personnel.</p> <p>Continuous training and updating of Open Science policies and procedures.</p> <p>Integration of Open Science practices into long-term planning and operations.</p>
The institution	<p>Designation of a contact person to promote open science both internal and European level.</p>	<p>Increased open science awareness within the institution.</p>	<p>Allocation of funds for the development and support of the OS Ambassador network.</p>	<p>Sustained investment in infrastructure to support Open Science initiatives.</p>

	<p>Immediate improvements in Open Science practices leading to a more robust research environment.</p> <p>An expert who supervises the implementation of the OS.</p> <p>Participation in events related to OS</p>	<p>Enhanced institutional visibility and prestige as a leader in Open Science. Development of policies that could attract more funding and higher-quality researchers.</p> <p>Attracting talent and collaborations due to a strong Open Science culture.</p> <p>Improved success in grant applications where Open Science is a criterion.</p> <p>Develop a holistic approach through a main point of contact for open science issues within EELISA institutions.</p> <p>To have a network of OS leaders in capacity to coordinate answers to scientific calls.</p> <p>Increasing the number of researchers involved in OS practices.</p>	<p>Institutional resources spent on promoting and integrating the OS Ambassador program.</p> <p>Time spent in creating the network and its promotion.</p>	<p>Potential need for new roles or departments to oversee Open Science strategies.</p> <p>Long-term commitment to cultural change within the institution towards Open Science.</p> <p>Since open science consists of many elements, the open science ambassador may need to be supported by a task force of relevant administrative and academic units to take a holistic approach to the issues addressed within the institution and across EELISA.</p> <p>Incorporation of new staff if the OS community growth.</p>
Society, broader community	<p>Access to the latest research findings and data.</p> <p>Increased public engagement with science and research processes.</p>	<p>Improved societal trust in scientific research through transparency and accessibility.</p> <p>Accelerated innovation and problem-solving through widespread access to research outputs.</p> <p>To facilitate communication concerning the outputs.</p> <p>Increasing the transparency of institutions.</p>	<p>Public funds may be required to support Open Science initiatives and Ambassador programs.</p> <p>Initial resistance or lack of engagement from the broader community until the benefits of Open Science are realized.</p>	<p>Sustained public investment in Open Science infrastructure (e.g., databases, repositories).</p> <p>Continuous education and outreach efforts to maintain public interest and support for Open Science.</p>
ERA and European Union	<p>Alignment with European Open Science policies, increasing the region's competitiveness.</p> <p>Strengthening of the European Research Area through shared Open Science practices.</p> <p>A better implementation of open science principles in EELISA institutions.</p>	<p>Consolidation of the European Union's position as a global leader in Open Science.</p> <p>Long-term cultural change towards more collaborative and transparent research practices across member states.</p> <p>Formation of a community of experts that can be integrated in future work groups.</p>	<p>Potential for short-term misalignment with existing research policies and frameworks.</p>	<p>Funds allocated from EU budgets to kickstart and support OS Ambassador programs across member states.</p> <p>Long-term financial commitment to maintaining and scaling up the OS Ambassador programs.</p> <p>Continuous coordination with member states to ensure alignment with overarching EU Open Science strategies.</p>

		Contribution to ERA Action 1: Enable the open sharing of knowledge and the re-use of research outputs, including through the development of the European open science cloud (EOSC)		
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17) Innovative Distributed OS training Hub (D3.4, task 3.3)

Benefit (positive outcomes and negative outcomes avoided)		Cost (resources expended, both financial and non-financial, and negative outcomes)	
Short-term: benefits within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term	Short-term: costs within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term (<i>some costs indicated should be construed more as risks that could materialize</i>)
<p>Researchers & innovators</p> <p>The partnership will jointly define an Innovative Distributed Training Hub, along with Open Science training content and delivery methods specifications, using a common pool of resources. The goal is to create an effective training hub that promotes the adoption of Open Science principles and boosts OS skills.</p> <p>More opportunities to learn open science practices.</p> <p>Support the creation of an open science culture in the alliance.</p> <p>Harmonization of the OS training tools</p> <p>Increasing the OS skills of researchers.</p> <p>Improving the position of EELISA researchers.</p> <p>Increasing the visibility of researchers' work by adopting OS practices</p>	<p>Integration of Open Science concepts in educational programs and career development.</p> <p>Mandatory Open Science training for all research levels promoting a standard of excellence in research.</p> <p>To gain time and manpower in open science skills development and awareness studies.</p> <p>Increasing the number of citations in publications, data and software.</p>	<p>Resources allocated for the technical development of the OS course catalogue.</p> <p>Time invested in uploading OS courses and translating materials.</p> <p>Time and Resources spent for technical development of OS catalogue.</p> <p>Difficulties in receiving OS courses proposals from partners.</p> <p>Time spent learning new skills</p>	<p>Continuous updating of new training courses to keep up with evolving Open Science practices.</p> <p>Potential challenges in sourcing course proposals from partners.</p> <p>Need for budget allocation to support common infrastructure (for EELISA institutions without preferred infrastructure)</p>
<p>Administrative staff</p> <p>Opportunities to learn specific open science practice for administrative staff and librarians.</p> <p>Increasing their skills.</p>	<p>Specialized training provided for Open Science support roles, enhancing institutional efficiency.</p> <p>Increasing their capacity to finding new publications solutions. Eventually will reduce costs in resources.</p>	<p>Management of the OS training catalogue, including updates and rule-setting for access by external users.</p> <p>Overwork related with the deployment of the computational resources used for the hub.</p>	<p>Ongoing administrative effort to keep the training catalogue relevant and up-to-date.</p> <p>Support for external users engaging with the hub.</p> <p>Overwork due to maintain the infrastructure deployed.</p>
<p>The institution</p> <p>Shared resources among partners for Open Science training content development.</p> <p>Sharing educational materials between institutions.</p>	<p>Creation of micro-credentials and promotion of indicators to incentivize Open Science.</p> <p>Extensive catalogue of educational material related to OS.</p>	<p>Resources spent on creating the training catalogue and risk of underutilization by the research community.</p> <p>Time spent in preparing the material.</p>	<p>Risk of discontinuation of use upon the completion of EELISA InnoCORE, impacting the sustainability of the hub.</p> <p>Maintenance costs associated to the hub.</p>

				Time spent in updating the material.
Society, broader community	Networking events within the Open Science community promoting mutual growth. Accessing to educational materials.	Contributions of citizen science to university missions and broader community engagement. Removing inequalities in education	Possible perception of redundancy in course modules within the network.	Risk of discontinuation of use upon the completion of EELISA InnoCORE, affecting community access to resources.
ERA and European Union	Increased knowledge transfer to foster integration with Open Science ERA dimensions and EU policies. Sharing educational materials with other European institutions.	Opportunities for participation in EU program competitions related to Open Science. Increasing the number of people involved in OS. Contribution to ERA Action 1: Enable the open sharing of knowledge and the re-use of research outputs, including through the development of the European open science cloud (EOSC)	Complex bureaucratic procedures and access challenges to external infrastructure.	Potential reduction in research funding and dedicated funds for Open Science support due to overlapping resources.

ITM6 Involvement of citizens, civil society and public/cities authorities in research and innovation

18) EELISA Innovation Talks (WP7)

	Benefit (positive outcomes and negative outcomes avoided)		Cost (resources expended, both financial and non-financial, and negative outcomes)	
	Short-term: benefits within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term	Short-term: costs within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term (<i>some costs indicated should be construed more as risks that could materialize</i>)
Researchers & innovators	<p>Greater visibility for their research and innovation.</p> <p>Knowledge sharing.</p> <p>Inspiration and motivation</p> <p>Networking opportunities</p> <p>Awareness and education.</p> <p>Community building.</p>	<p>Increased societal relevance and impact of research projects through direct involvement of citizens and authorities, leading to research that is more aligned with societal needs and challenges.</p>	<p>Time needed for the preparation of the event.</p>	
Administrative staff	<p>Gained new competences by organizing EELISA Innovation Talks (e.g. how to live stream on YouTube)</p>	<p>Gained new competences by organizing EELISA Innovation Talks (e.g. how to live stream on YouTube)</p>	<p>Time and resources needed to organize the events.</p>	
The institution	<p>Greater outreach to society through EELISA Innovation Talks.</p> <p>A good way to promote EELISA within the institution (if the event was successful)</p>	<p>Strengthened ties with the local community and authorities, enhancing the institution's role as a societal actor and increasing its potential for societal impact.</p>	<p>Maybe there were too many EELISA Innovation Talks (fewer events with more resources put into them might have been the better solution)</p> <p>Allocation of resources for the organisation.</p> <p>All: Financial expenses: Time and resources: Planning and coordinating innovation talks require significant time and resources from organizers. This includes tasks such as securing speakers, promoting the event, managing registrations, and logistical arrangements.</p> <p>Risk of low attendance:</p> <p>Logistical Challenges.</p>	

Society, broader community	New insights into research and innovation topics	Direct involvement in research and innovation processes allows for a greater understanding of scientific research, fostering a more informed and engaged public.	English speaking format created a barrier to the broader community: Only a relatively small audience could be reached in some cases.	
ERA and European Union	<p>Establishment of European research and innovation outreach formats.</p> <p>Public events reinforce the visibility of the added-value of the EU. Help building an EU ownership feeling.</p> <p>Greater promotion of EU funded research.</p> <p>Contribution to ERA action 14: Bring science closer to citizens</p>	<p>Promotes a model of inclusive and participatory research that aligns with European values of innovation democracy, potentially setting a standard for future EU research initiatives.</p> <p>Contributes to the realization of a European Research Area that is inclusive, innovative, and reflective of the diverse needs and aspirations of its citizens.</p> <p>Contribution to ERA action 14: Bring science closer to citizens</p>	If the event is not successful, they can create a feeling of wasted public money.	If the event is not successful, they can create a feeling of wasted public money.

19) EELISA Prototype Contest (WP7)

Benefit (positive outcomes and negative outcomes avoided)		Cost (resources expended, both financial and non-financial, and negative outcomes)	
Short-term: benefits within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term	Short-term: costs within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term (<i>some costs indicated should be construed more as risks that could materialize</i>)
<p>Researchers & innovators</p> <p>New opportunities for innovators for testing their prototypes and, therefore, put their products/services into the market, opportunity to showcase their innovative ideas and prototypes to a wider audience.</p> <p>Improved access to new markets</p> <p>Increased visibility for the product/service</p> <p>New training opportunities in co-creation and entrepreneurship methods.</p> <p>Gained improved skills and knowledge of innovation and co-creation methods that will help researchers and innovators for the rest of their careers to build more successful products and services.</p> <p>Networking with other startups at the EELISA x JOSEPHS co-creation workshops.</p> <p>Access to feedback and mentorship from experts and peers in their field.</p> <p>Recognition and validation of their research efforts and innovative solutions.</p>	<p>Improved success of start-ups incubated at EELISA partners</p> <p>Gained improved skills and knowledge of innovation and co-creation methods that will help researchers and innovators for the rest of their careers to build more successful products and services.</p> <p>Long-lasting partnerships with other innovators, startups, and industry partners met through the contest.</p>	<p>Time spent in the preparation of the proposal</p> <p>ALL: Limited access or participation for certain segments of the community due to barriers such as location or resources.</p> <p>Need for ongoing support and infrastructure to translate prototypes into tangible societal benefits.</p> <p>Consideration of ethical and social implications of the technologies or solutions presented.</p> <p>Management of expectations regarding the immediate impact or timeline for implementation of prototypes.</p> <p>Risk of intellectual property exposure, especially if prototypes are not adequately protected.</p> <p>Allocation of resources for planning, organizing, and managing the contest logistics.</p>	<p>Time spent in the preparation of the proposal and the testing, but product or service not successful in the end.</p>
<p>Administrative staff</p> <p>New insights into innovation and co-creation methods.</p> <p>Acquisition of new skills in managing innovation contests and co-creation workshops.</p> <p>Opportunity to support and facilitate innovation within the institution.</p>	<p>New insights into innovation and co-creation methods.</p> <p>Development of a robust framework for organizing future contests and innovation activities.</p> <p>Strengthened relationships with external partners and stakeholders through ongoing contest management.</p>	<p>Time and resources needed to organize the EELISA prototype contests</p> <p>Potential challenges in managing logistics and coordination with multiple stakeholders.</p>	

	<p>Engagement with researchers and innovators across different departments and disciplines.</p> <p>Showcase of the institution's commitment to fostering creativity and entrepreneurship.</p> <p>Networking opportunities with external partners, sponsors, and judges involved in the contest</p>			
The institution	<p>Improved opportunities within the innovation ecosystem</p> <p>Visibility to start-ups and innovators in each institution's ecosystem.</p> <p>Promotion of interdisciplinary collaboration and knowledge exchange.</p> <p>Strengthening of ties with industry partners and potential sponsors.</p> <p>Contribution to the institution's strategic goals related to innovation and societal impact.</p> <p>Creation of opportunities for students and faculty to engage with real-world problems and solution.</p>	<p>Enhanced capacity for commercialization of research outputs through proven success in prototype development.</p>	<p>Allocation of staff and resources to support participants.</p> <p>ALL: Limited access or participation for certain segments of the community due to barriers such as location or resources.</p> <p>Need for ongoing support and infrastructure to translate prototypes into tangible societal benefits.</p> <p>Consideration of ethical and social implications of the technologies or solutions presented.</p> <p>Management of expectations regarding the immediate impact or timeline for implementation of prototypes.</p> <p>Risk of intellectual property exposure, especially if prototypes are not adequately protected.</p> <p>Allocation of resources for planning, organizing, and managing the contest logistics.</p>	<p>Possible need for additional training or hiring of staff skilled in managing innovation ecosystems.</p>
Society, broader community	<p>Possibility to participate in innovation processes and participate in the design of products /services adapted to real user needs</p>	<p>Better products /services adapted to real user needs</p> <p>Strengthened innovation culture, encouraging more individuals to participate in innovation and entrepreneurship.</p>		

<p>ERA and European Union</p>	<p>Immediate demonstration of the EU's commitment to fostering innovation and entrepreneurship.</p> <p>Showcase of EU-funded research and innovation projects contributing to societal challenges and economic growth.</p> <p>Enhanced visibility of EU support for startups and innovators, particularly in leveraging test bed infrastructures.</p> <p>Promotion of collaboration and knowledge sharing among researchers and institutions across Europe.</p> <p>Alignment with EU priorities and initiatives aimed at fostering innovation and research excellence.</p> <p>Contribution to the objectives of the European Research Area (ERA) by promoting interdisciplinary research and innovation.</p> <p>Strengthening of the European innovation ecosystem through the identification and support of promising prototypes.</p>	<p>Improved success of start-ups incubated in Europe thanks to the access to markets different from the market of origin since their inception</p>		<p>Need for using the existing test bed infrastructures of EU for these competitions.</p>
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ITM7 Exploring joint structures across the European Universities on technical activities common to all “European Universities”

20) Participation in FOREU meetings and activities, including events organised by other alliances (CHARM-EU, Exper, CIVIS)

	Benefit (positive outcomes and negative outcomes avoided)		Cost (resources expended, both financial and non-financial, and negative outcomes)	
	Short-term: benefits within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term	Short-term: costs within the timeframe of EELISA InnoCORE (36 months)	Long-term (<i>some costs indicated should be construed more as risks that could materialize</i>)
Researchers & innovators	<p>Exchange of good practices between institutions.</p> <p>Learning from the first hand especially from EU Officials.</p> <p>Access to research and innovation trends.</p> <p>Strengthening of interdisciplinary research through diverse interactions.</p>	<p>Establishment of long-lasting research partnerships and networks.</p> <p>Contribution to the advancement of their fields with innovative solutions.</p> <p>Enhanced reputation and recognition within the academic and innovation communities.</p>	<p>Time spent in participating in these meetings, activities</p>	<p>Maintenance of international collaborations may require sustained financial and time investments.</p>
Administrative staff	<p>Increased networking opportunities.</p> <p>Improvement of skills thanks to the mutual learning exercise.</p> <p>Exchange of good practices between institutions.</p> <p>Learning from the first hand especially from EU Officials.</p> <p>Exposure to diverse administrative practices and policies.</p> <p>Development of project management skills through collaboration on international projects.</p>	<p>Contribution to the institutional legacy through the implementation of innovative administrative practices.</p>	<p>Time spent in participating in these meetings, activities</p>	<p>Need for continuous professional development to keep up with evolving practices.</p>
The institution	<p>Greater visibility at EU-level.</p> <p>Improvement of actions (resources, instruments, policies, governance structures) put in place by the Alliance, thanks to the inspiration from other Alliances (mutual-learning exercise).</p>	<p>Better performance of the Alliance thanks to improved actions (resources, instruments, policies, governance structures) via the mutual learning exercises.</p>	<p>Time and resources spent in participating in the meetings and events, and contributing to documents.</p>	<p>Commitment to long-term financial contributions to sustain alliance activities and partnerships.</p>

	<p>Improvement of actions put in place by the Alliance, thanks to the example of errors and things that did not work for other Alliances.</p> <p>Stronger voice in EU affairs.</p> <p>Early information about calls for proposals as well as policy initiatives relevant for both the Alliance and the individual universities</p>			
Society, broader community	<p>Recognition of public entities in supporting the university Alliance.</p>	<p>Excellent HEIs, excellent education, excellent campuses providing citizens with the best education and skills, via the full deployment of Alliances.</p> <p>Better and more higher education possibilities, via the full deployment of Alliances.</p>		<p>Public resources spent in non-performing or failed Alliances.</p>
ERA and European Union	<p>An opportunity to get in touch with European Universities.</p> <p>Contribution to ERA Action 13 Empower higher education institutions to develop in line with the era, and in synergy with the european education area.</p>	<p>Better and more efficient use of public resources due to improvement of actions by peer learning.</p> <p>Strengthened European Research Area (ERA) through cohesive and collaborative efforts across borders.</p> <p>Long-term sustainability of higher education improvements through structured alliance frameworks.</p> <p>Contribution to ERA Action 13 Empower higher education institutions to develop in line with the era, and in synergy with the European education area.</p>		<p>Potential for overlap and redundancy among alliances, leading to inefficiencies.</p>

Annex III - Scores per partner

Action	Benefit										Cost									
	UPM	SSSA	SNS	FAU	BME	UPB	PSL	ENPC	ITÜ	Average	UPM	SSSA	SNS	FAU	BME	UPB	PSL	ENPC	ITÜ	Average
1) Mapping SRAs	12	48	48	27	36	48	48	36	48	39	36	48	32	12	32	8	48	24	48	32
2) Portfolio challenges Communities	8	8	27	8	18	27	27	27	27	20	1	27	9	2	16	18	27	27	27	17
3) R&I Symposia	36	48	27	64	18	27	48	48	48	40	9	48	6	4	48	2	48	48	48	29
4) Networking Platform (EINP)	27	64	18	27	36	64	36	18	24	35	12	36	12	27	24	36	36	36	36	28
5) EELISA Connect call	48	64	12	64	64	64	64	64	64	56	36	18	3	8	2	1	36	18	36	18
6) Gender Equality Work Group	48	24	36	64	8	27	48	18	36	34	6	18	8	6	2	12	18	9	18	11
7) Policy Liaisons Board	36	18	18	48	27	64	36	18	24	32	2	48	6	2	8	1	12	12	12	11
8) Catalogue of facilities	4	8	36	36	8	64	36	12	16	24	36	64	36	18	32	36	32	36	32	36
9) Infrastructure strategy	4	18	9	8	12	64	27	12	18	19	24	36	16	2	48	48	36	27	36	30
10) Tech transfer initiatives	6	8	16	8	27	27	12	12	12	14	6	27	6	24	18	18	27	27	27	20
11) Industrial Chair	27	4	2	27	27	27	6	4	4	14	36	4	18	16	4	8	4	2	4	11
12) Opening up entrep activities	36	24	24	64	48	64	64	48	48	47	2	18	2	1	6	12	18	18	18	11
13) Entrepreneurship School	27	48	24	64	18	64	4	27	4	31	2	8	4	4	4	12	8	12	8	7
14) Next Level competition	24	64	12	64	48	64	64	36	64	49	8	27	2	4	6	18	27	18	27	15
15) OS Toolkit	36	48	18	27	27	64	48	27	36	37	2	18	6	8	12	48	12	12	12	14
16) OS Ambassadors	12	18	12	36	27	64	24	12	12	24	27	18	6	8	4	27	6	12	6	13
17) OS training Hub	8	18	4	27	18	64	27	18	18	22	8	12	4	4	8	48	12	12	12	13
18) Innovation Talks	18	8	27	36	36	27	24	27	12	24	6	12	2	18	3	4	12	27	12	11
19) Prototype Contest	27	36	9	64	64	64	36	27	36	40	8	27	1	4	8	18	27	27	27	16
20) FOREU	36	27	9	36	36	64	36	27	36	34	1	12	16	2	3	12	6	1	6	7